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1. Executive Summary

Marine ecosystems are increasingly affected by pollutants and human-induced pressures, leading to significant environmental and ecological concerns. Deliverable 8.2 of the NECCON project reports on advancements in WP8, focusing on the development and improvement of models to assess the fate, transport, and impact of pollutants and anthropogenic stressors in marine environments.

This deliverable presents the methodologies and progress made in modelling microplastics, persistent organic pollutants (POPs), mercury, and oil spills, alongside assessments of fisheries pressure.

Key outcomes:

- **Microplastics modeling:** Improved representation of plastic fragmentation and biofouling processes, integrating new size classes and validation datasets. These advancements enable better tracking of plastic distribution and potential ingestion by marine organisms, supporting targeted mitigation strategies.
- **Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs):** Implementation of marine POP chemistry, accounting for photodegradation, bioaccumulation, and partitioning dynamics. These improvements will support risk assessments for regulatory frameworks and pollution mitigation policies.
- **Mercury modeling:** Enhanced seawater-atmosphere exchange processes and integration with biogeochemical cycles, including dynamic interactions with phytoplankton and zooplankton. This contributes to more accurate predictions of mercury bioaccumulation risks for marine food webs.
- **Oil spill modeling:** Refinements in oil transport and weathering processes, improving the capability to forecast spill dispersion and degradation under various environmental conditions. These developments provide critical information for emergency response planning.
- **Fisheries pressure modeling:** New methods to assess bottom trawling impacts on benthic habitats and organisms, informing sustainable fisheries management and marine conservation efforts.

A first description of model validation efforts, ensuring accuracy through comparisons with observational data, is provided here. However, a more comprehensive evaluation and comparison with those already in use by CMEMS and other WPs will be conducted in the coming months.

These developments contribute to NECCON's overarching goal of enhancing marine monitoring and prediction capabilities. The improvements in pollution and fisheries pressure modeling can support the development of new CMEMS products, offering operational tools for tracking pollutants, assessing ecosystem risks, and informing policymakers and stakeholders on marine environmental status. This work aligns with European and global environmental directives such as the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

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2. Scope

This deliverable presents the development, refinement, and validation of numerical models that simulate the transport, transformation, and ecological effects of pollutants in the marine systems.

The work was covered in Tasks 8.2 and 8.3 and focuses on:

- Advancing pollutant modelling for microplastics, oil spills, POPs, and mercury to improve tracking and impact assessments.
- Developing fisheries pressure models to quantify trawling impacts on benthic ecosystems.
- Implementing different validation strategies, according to the different stages of the model advancements and considering data availability.

The findings in this deliverable aim to provide a foundation for future model integration efforts of pollution and stressors models in CMEMS.

We also highlight here that HEREON provided an Inkind contribution, not initially planned in the DoA, in terms of Hg, POPs, PFAS datasets.

3. Introduction

The Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) provides essential ocean monitoring and forecasting services but currently lacks dedicated forecasts and assessments for marine pollution and other pressures. Understanding the transport, transformation, and ecological impact of pollutants and anthropogenic stressors is critical for effective marine conservation and planning. In response to this need, WP8 of the NECCTON project focuses on improving numerical models that assess pollution fate, fisheries impacts, and cumulative environmental stressors.

This deliverable presents the latest advancements in pollutant modeling, covering microplastics, persistent organic pollutants (POPs), mercury, and oil spills, along with assessments of fisheries pressure. The research integrates hydrodynamic-biogeochemical coupling and pollutant transport modeling to enhance predictive capabilities. The relevant code for each model can be found on GitHub, at <https://github.com/neccton-algo>.

This report outlines the rationale for selecting and refining pollutant and stressor models, key advancements and improvements in model parameterization and performance.

To **further** improve marine pollution modeling, future developments should integrate additional interactions with high trophic level (HTL) organisms, recognizing their significant role in pollutant transport and transformation. Currently, different models incorporate marine biota interactions with varying levels of complexity: in the mercury and POP's models, interactions with phytoplankton and zooplankton are dynamically represented, accounting for bioaccumulation, trophic transfer, and their seasonality. In contrast, biota interactions are absent in the models for microplastics and oil spills. Although these interactions introduce complexity, and then uncertainty, incorporating biotic dynamics into pollutant models will enhance accuracy. Strengthening the connection between

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physical-chemical transport models and ecological processes will be crucial for advancing CMEMS products and improving our understanding of pollution impacts on marine ecosystems.

4. Marine litter and microplastics

4.1 Introduction

Marine litter and microplastics have emerged as critical environmental concerns due to their widespread presence in the world's oceans and their impact on marine ecosystems and human health. Microplastics (<5 mm in size) are particularly problematic because of their ability to persist in marine environments, interact with biological processes, and infiltrate food chains, potentially leading to bioaccumulation. Macroplastics (>5 mm) contribute to the degradation of marine habitats and provide the primary source for secondary microplastics through fragmentation.

Two different models for Plastic transport and processes on the marine environment are used in the project: Plastic Poseidon, developed by HCMR - MINDS and applied to the Mediterranean Sea, and Plasticparcels, developed by UU and applied to the Arctic and the Northwest Shelf.

The HCMR-MINDS Plastic Poseidon model is a 3-D coupled hydrodynamic/Lagrangian particle drift model, developed to study the dispersion of plastics originated from land-based sources (cities and rivers) in the Mediterranean (Tsiaras et al., 2021). The model takes into account the most important processes (advection from currents, Stokes drift, vertical/horizontal mixing, sinking, wind drag, beaching). The model considers different sizes and types of micro- and macroplastics: Four size classes (350, 500, 1000, 2000 μm) of microplastics and five sizes/types (5 mm–2 cm, 2–20 cm, > 20 cm bottles, > 20 cm bags, > 20 cm foam) of macroplastics. All sizes/types of plastics are affected by Stokes drift (obtained from Copernicus Marine Service), while low density macroplastics (i.e., bottles and foam) are also subject to wind drag following the Yoon et al. (2010) parameterization. Moreover, biofouling of microplastics, a mechanism potentially explaining the MPs removal from surface water, is explicitly described, as a function of bacterial abundance, (obtained from the biogeochemical model simulation) that is considered as a proxy for the biofouling community. Particles that arrive on land are assumed to remain on the beach for a fixed retention time, after which they return to the sea. During the time they spend on the beach, the particles' concentration decreases, assuming some loss rate due to burial. Within NECCTON, the existing model has been upgraded and refined, including a better representation of microplastics size distribution, retention time on beaches, and a model parameterization for plastics fragmentation. Moreover, additional in situ data have been compiled for model validation, including all available field observations from databases (EMODNET) and several recent publications on micro- and macroplastics (in addition to those used in Tsiaras et al 2021). The code for this model can be found on GitHub at https://github.com/tamvas3712/Plastic_Poseidon.

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Plasticparcels, a 3-D offline Lagrangian plastic dispersion model, has been developed by the UU for use with existing and future hydrodynamic model output (Denes & van Sebille, 2024). Based on the parcels computational Lagrangian ocean analysis framework (Delandmeter & van Sebille, 2019; Lange & van Sebille, 2017), Plasticparcels provides new capability for advecting virtual plastic particles with a wide range of physical properties. The tool applies a collection of physical processes to the virtual particles, such as Stokes drift, wind-induced drift, biofouling, and turbulent vertical mixing, via custom particle behaviour programmed in the form of “kernels”. In addition to the fine-scale physics parameterisations, Plasticparcels provides global particle initialisation maps that represent best estimates for plastic pollution emissions along coastlines (Jambeck et al., 2015), from river sources (Meijer et al., 2021), and in the open-ocean from fishing-related activities (Kroodsmas et al., 2018), as well as a current best estimate of buoyant plastic concentrations globally (Kaandorp et al., 2023). The code for this model can be found on GitHub at <https://github.com/OceanParcels/plasticparcels>.

4.2 Plastics fragmentation in the HCMR-MINDS Plastics model.

4.2.1 Background

Fragmentation plays an important role in explaining the observed size distribution of plastics and to provide a long-term mass budget analysis on plastics accumulation in the marine environment and potential future trends under different scenarios (e.g. Kaandorp et al., 2023; Lebreton et al., 2019). Several studies have shown that the majority of marine plastic litter in the global ocean are fragments resulting from the breakdown of larger plastic items (e.g. Czar et al 2014; Suaria et al 2016; Eriksen et al., 2014). There is an on-going debate on the gap between the estimated load of plastics in the global ocean, being much higher as compared to the observed concentrations of floating plastics (e.g. Kaandorp et al., 2023; Czar et al 2014; Isobe et al., 2022). The absence of significant increasing trends in historical time-series of surface plastics concentration, despite the increasing trends of plastics production in recent decades suggest the existence of removal mechanisms of floating plastics from the sea surface, such as beaching, biofouling/ingestion and fragmentation (e.g. Czar et al., 2014). The progressive fragmentation of plastic items into smaller pieces leads to relatively higher abundance toward smaller sizes, described by a power-law distribution. While such a distribution fits well with observations at larger sizes, the observed size distribution indicates a strong decrease of smaller size (<1mm) microplastics, suggesting a potential removal mechanism from the surface water. Smaller size microplastics may be ingested by marine organisms, while the increasing surface/volume ratio with decreasing size also favours biofouling induced sinking from the attachment of heavier organisms. Physical processes (e.g. vertical mixing) can also have a size-selective influence on plastic particles, decreasing the near surface concentration. Another removal mechanism could also be the progressive fragmentation towards very small sizes, undetectable with current sampling nets.

Fragmentation of plastics is primarily activated by ultraviolet (UV) radiation of sunlight, being also regulated by oxygen availability, temperature and mechanical abrasion (Andrady, 2011, 2017; Song et al., 2017). Thus, fragmentation is more likely on beaches or inland waters, where plastics are subjected to UV-radiation and higher temperatures, causing their embrittlement and subsequent breaking down with mechanical abrasion (e.g. waves). This mechanism is significantly retarded in the seawater, due to lower ambient temperatures and reduced oxygen and UV radiation that is further inhibited by

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biofouling, while other types of degradation processes, such as hydrolysis and bio-degradation are considered much slower, as compared to light-induced oxidation, at least for commonly found polymers (e.g., polyethylene) in the marine environment (Andrady, 2011; Booth et al., 2018).

4.2.2. Theory

The fragmentation rate of plastics on beaches or at sea is still very poorly quantified, with very few experimental studies (e.g. Song et al., 2017; Kalogerakis et al., 2017). Song et al (2017) studied the fragmentation of microplastics, after 12 months of laboratory UV exposure (roughly equivalent with 4.2 years of environmental exposure), followed by 2 months of mechanical abrasion with sand, representative of beach conditions in South Korea. In particular, a pellet of ~26 mm³ (size ~3 mm), made of polyethylene (PE), the most abundant polymer in the Mediterranean, produced 20 ± 8.3 particles, dominated by small size (>17, 50-100 um) particles, while more than 90% of the initial particles remained intact. A relatively stronger fragmentation was found for polypropylene (PP) pellets (initial volume ~19 mm³), producing up to 6084 ± 1061 particles/pellet, with ~80% of the initial particle remaining intact.

Kaandorp et al. (2021) proposed a continuous cascading fragmentation model, based on fractal theory (Charalambous et al., 2015), describing the continuous size-distribution of mass (m) and number (n) of fragments, resulting from fragmentation of a parent object to smaller particles of size class k as:

$$m(k; f, p) = \frac{\Gamma(k + f)}{\Gamma(k + 1)\Gamma(f)} p^k (1 - p)^f, n(k, f, p) = 2^{D_N k} m(k, f, p) \quad \text{Eq.(4.1)}$$

with f being a fragmentation index, p the fraction of the parent object that fragments into smaller particles at $f=1$, Γ the gamma function and D_N the spatial dimension (i.e. $D_N=3$ for 3-D objects such as cubes/spheres and $D_N=2$ for 2-D objects such as sheets). Parameters p and f were calibrated using the observed size distribution from Song et al. (2017) fragmentation experimental data. Onink et al. (2022) has also implemented the Kaandorp et al. (2021) fragmentation model, being customized to a Lagrangian model for the Mediterranean. Aoki et al. (2021) has also proposed another theoretical fragmentation model, based on statistical mechanics, assuming that fragmentation into smaller pieces requires progressively larger energy with decreasing size, in an attempt to explain the observed size distribution of plastics in the global ocean (e.g. Cozar et al., 2014; Isobe et al., 2021),

4.2.3 Implementation

The Kaandorp et al. (2021) fragmentation model describes a continuous size distribution and is not directly applicable with our model, which explicitly describes the size of plastic items (grouped in super-individuals). Moreover, due to computational constraints, a limited number of new size classes could be practically added in each fragmentation event, in which case volume/mass conservation would not be totally guaranteed, applying the Kaandorp model (Onink et al., 2022). Therefore, a simplified fragmentation model with volume conservation was empirically fitted with Song et al. (2017) data (see Figure 4.2.1). Starting with the same parent objects (polyethylene (PE)~26 mm³, size ~3 mm, polypropylene (PP)~19 mm³, size ~3 mm), a fitted percentage is assumed to be fragmented to

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gradually smaller size classes, following Kaandorp et al. (2021) cascading approach. Five size classes (including the parent object) were chosen ($k=1, 4, 8, 11, 14$) to cover the range of the observed distribution. The abundance and volume/size of different size classes are then calculated as:

$$n(k) = n_0 \times div \times p(k), vol(k) = vol_0 \times 1/div, size(k) = size_0 \times (1/div)^{(1/D)} \quad \text{Eq.(4.2)}$$

with $div=2^{(k-1)}$, $n_0=1$ and vol_0/siz_0 the volume/size of the parent object. A spatial dimension $D=2.5$ was chosen to account for a mixture of 3-D particles (particles occupying a 3-dimensional volume) and 2-D particles (particles occupying a 2-d surface, such as plastic films, plastic bag pieces) as in Onink et al. (2022) and Kaandorp et al. (2023).

Different percentages $p(k=1,5)$ for each size class were fitted for PE and PP to

$p(\text{PE}) = [0.992, 0.005, 0.001, 0.0011, 0.0012]$ and $p(\text{PP}) = [0.828, 0.005, 0.006, 0.011, 0.15]$.

Where $p(k=1)$ represents the percentage of the parent object that remains intact. This was applied on the abundance $n(1)$ of the parent particle, rather than its volume/size, as currently volume and mass distribution of particles is not yet consistently described through the entire range of both micro- and macroplastics in the model. Thus, in practice, in the Lagrangian model simulation described below, a percentage $1-p(1)$ of the parent particles is assumed to be fragmented, with the rest of the particles remaining intact. This allows a more transparent evaluation of the effect of fragmentation, given the current model limitations.

Figure 4.2.1. Size distribution of fragments produced from PE (blue) and PP (red) plastic pellets, simulated with Kaandorp et al. (2021) model (solid line) and the present model (stars), against experimental data from Song et al. (2017) (dots).

The same procedure is applied for the Mediterranean Lagrangian model simulation, using the fitted parameters for polyethylene (PE), the most abundant plastic in the Mediterranean (Zeri et al., 2018; Liorca et al., 2020). n_0 and siz_0 are replaced by the number and size of the (parent) super-individual (SI) particles with four additional SIs being created at each fragmentation event. A fragmentation time counter ($Tfrag$), representative of ageing, is assigned to all particles and keeps track of the time a super-individual remains on a beach. When this fragmentation time reaches a specified fragmentation time scale ($Tfrag_0$), a fragmentation event takes place, following the procedure described above. The fragmentation time scale was specified to $1/5$ ($Tfrag_0=0.84$ years) of the 4.2 years of environmental

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exposure in Song et al (2017) experimental setup, in order to speed up the effect of fragmentation and approach a steady state after a relatively short 5-year simulation. A series of 5-year simulations were performed to investigate the effect of fragmentation (see Table 4.2.1). In Run1, the same fragmentation time ($T_{frag0}=0.84$ years) is assumed for all micro- and macroplastics size classes, while input sources are assumed to be fresh particles (i.e. no ageing, $T_{frag}=0$). In Run2, input sources are assumed to have some initial ageing ($T_{frag}>0$), which is relatively higher for rivers and coastal cities macroplastics and smaller for wastewater microplastics, being randomly selected, based on an exponentially decreasing probability distribution (see Figure 4.2.2). In Run3, ageing of input sources is the same as Run2, but a shorter fragmentation time scale is assumed with increasing size (microplastics: $T_{frag0}=0.84$, macro 5-20mm: $T_{frag0}=0.8$, macro 20-200mm: $T_{frag0}=0.7$, macro>200mm: $T_{frag0}=0.6$ years), following the hypothesis of Aoki et al. (2021). In Run0, no fragmentation is applied.

Table 4.2.1. Description of different simulations attributes

Run0	No Fragmentation
Run1	$T_{frag0}=0.84$ all sizes, initial $T_{frag}=0$ on sources
Run2	$T_{frag0}=0.84$ all sizes, initial $T_{frag}>0$ on source
Run3	$T_{frag0}=0.84$ micro, 0.8 macro 5-20mm, 0.7 macro 20-200m, 0.6 macro>200mm initial $T_{frag}>0$ on sources

Figure 4.2.2. Sources ageing probability distribution $p(T_{frag})=\exp[-T_{frag}/(0.5*T_{frag0}*factor)]$, with factor=0.4 for rivers/beaches and factor=0.2 for wastewater microplastics.

Other improvements

The model considered 6 different (50, 100, 350, 500, 1000, 2000 μm) size-classes for microplastics. Moreover, fragmentation was implicitly taken into account, assuming a decreasing abundance with size (input \sim size^{-1.3}) for microplastics sources, following Lindeque et al. (2020). The effect of biofouling induced sinking, being stronger for small size classes, combined with the assumed decreasing function with size on sources, resulted in a size distribution (peak at 1000 μm , see Figure 4.2.3), which was consistent with observations (Cozar et al, 2014; 2015, see also Figure 4.2.7). In order to refine the

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representation of microplastics size distribution, a varying microplastics size on sources was assumed, following the same decreasing function. Initially, different variants with random sizes within the microplastics range (300-5000 μm) were tested. However, given the limited number of super-individuals added in each source to represent different size classes (4-10), the resulting size distribution (of sources) significantly deviated from the expected theoretical function. Instead, the theoretical function was closely approximated with a perpetual 19-day repeating sampling from fixed sizes with a 50 μm step (see Figure 4.2.4).

Figure 4.2.3: Normalized mean (2010-2017) size distribution of near surface microplastics, simulated with Tsiaras et al. (2021) model, with biofouling induced sinking (left) and without (right).

Figure 4.2.4: Size distribution of microplastics input sources with applied 19-day repeating sampling from fixed sizes with a 50 μm step, against the theoretical ($\sim \text{size}^{-1.3}$) distribution.

Another model modification was related to retention time on beaches. Tsiaras et al. (2021) adopted a relatively small (microplastics ~ 1 day, macroplastics ~ 2 days) retention time on beaches, combined with a relatively high burial loss, which was a tuned parameter to obtain a best fit with floating plastics observations. Given the importance of the plastics retention time on beaches with regard to fragmentation (see discussion above), this was significantly increased, while also decreasing burial loss in order to obtain similar results for floating plastics. For microplastics, the retention time (*rtime*) was assumed to be a linear function of the particle's size dependent terminal rise velocity (*wb*), following Hinata et al. (2017):

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$$r_{time} \text{ (days)} = 260 * w_b \text{ (m/s)} + 7.1,$$

Eq.4.3

This results in retention times varying between 10 (0.3mm) and 20 (5mm) days. A gradually higher retention time was adopted for macroplastics (5mm-2.5cm: 20 days, 2.5cm-20cm: 30 days, >20cm: 50days).

4.2.4 Validation

In Figure 4.2.7, the simulated size distribution from the 5-year simulations is shown against a mean distribution from observations in the global ocean (Cozar et al., 2014). A good agreement is found, showing a peak around 1mm and decreasing for smaller size (0.3-1mm) microplastics. The simulations with fragmentation (Run1-3) show a slightly higher abundance for small size (0.3-0.4 mm) microplastics, as compared to the simulation without fragmentation (Run0). This is probably related to the relatively higher increase of smaller size microplastics due to fragmentation (see Figure 4.2.9), suggesting that a slightly faster biofouling induced sinking or differential burial loss for microplastics should be adopted in conjunction with fragmentation.

In Figure 4.2.8, the near surface (0-0.3m) microplastics (>300µm) distribution from different simulations is validated against available in situ data, as plotted in Figures 4.2.8 and 4.2.10. A reasonable agreement was found, both in terms of magnitude and horizontal variability (correlation 0.21-0.27, see also Figure 4.2.9), capturing most of the observed patterns, such as the increase of MPs in the Ligurian Sea, Sicily, Algerian basin and North Adriatic coastal areas or the relatively lower abundance in the Gulf of Lion. The main model deviation is the underestimated MPs abundance in the Balearic and Ionian Sea and the relatively overestimated/underestimated concentration along the Ligurian Sea coast and the Gulf of Lion (see also Tsiaras et al., 2021). Different simulations show quite similar results, both in terms of mean abundance and horizontal variability (see also Figure 4.2.9), with a slight increase of microplastics concentration in the simulations with fragmentation applied, particularly Run 2-3. In Figures 4.2.10-4.2.15, the macroplastics concentrations from different simulations are also compared against available data (as shown in Figures 4.2.8 and 4.2.10.) Differences among different simulations are relatively stronger, as compared to microplastics, particularly in terms of horizontal variability. The model shows a relatively poor skill (Pearson correlation ~0.13, p<0.05 in Run1, Run3; not statistically significant correlation in Run0, Run2) in capturing the smaller macroplastics (0.5-2 cm) point-by-point horizontal variability, but partly reproduces the variability among different areas (see Figure 4.2.12). A similar comparison is found for macroplastics (2-20 cm) (see Figure 4.2.13). We should note that such a point-to-point validation is quite challenging, considering the uncertainty of source inputs (see Tsiaras et al., 2021) and also the seasonal/inter-annual variability, which, currently, is not taken into account, given the relatively small amount of data. A better model skill may be seen for larger macroplastics >20cm (Pearson correlation 0.14-0.31, see Figures 4.2.14-4.2.15). A slight decrease of macroplastics concentration may be noticed (see Figure 4.2.14-4.2.15) in the simulations with fragmentation applied, showing a better agreement with data. Run3 simulation probably shows the best overall skill, considering both micro- and macroplastics comparison against in situ data.

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Figure 4.2.7. Mean (2010-2014) normalized relative abundance (abundance(size)/total abundance) size distribution, simulated in different experiments (Run0 blue line, Run1 red line, Run2 green line, Run3 magenta line), against the size distribution from observations in the global ocean (black line, Cozar et al., 2014). The observed size distribution was obtained from normalized (abundance/mm) data provided in Aoki et al. (2021), divided by the total abundance. Reference size in the model distribution was 0.1 mm of microplastics abundance. The macroplastics abundance was then divided by a different size range factor (macroplastics 0.5-2cm: 150, macroplastics 2-20 cm: 1800, macroplastics >20 cm: 3000) to obtain the normalized abundance as in Cozar et al. (2014).

Figure 4.2.8. Simulated near surface (0-0.3 m) microplastics mean (2010-2014) concentration (particles/m²) from different simulations, against available in-situ data. In situ data were obtained from: de Haan et al., (2019); Ruiz-Oregon et al., (2018); Ruiz-Oregon et al., (2016); Collignon et al., (2012); Schmidt et al., (2018); Pedrotti et al., (2016); Fossi et al., (2017); Faure et

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al., (2015), Vianello et al., (2018); Zeri et al., (2018); Eriksen et al., (2014); Gundogdu et al., (2018); Fossi et al., (2016); Panti et al., (2015); Bains et al., (2018); Gajšt et al., (2016); EMODnet (2020). Adamopoulou et al., (2021); Tsiaras et al., (2022); Trani et al., (2023); Zayen et al., (2021); Setiti et al., (2021); van der Hal et al., (2017); de Haan et al., (2022); Pedrotti et al., (2022); Ruiz-Oregon et al., (2019); Suaria et al., (2016); Vianello et al., (2018); Basurko et al., (2022); Marchetto et al., (2022); Caldwell et al., (2019); Caldwell et al., (2020); Jemaa 2021; Gedjk 2022; Pedrotti 2022;

Figure 4.2.9. Boxplot (left), indicating the range, median and 25th/75th percentiles and Taylor diagram (right) of mean (2010-2014) microplastics concentration (particles/m²) from different simulations, against in-situ data (see Figure 8).

Figure 4.2.10. Mean (2010-2014) concentration (#/Km²) of macroplastics 5mm-2cm from different simulations, against available in situ data. In situ data were obtained from: Sanchez et al., (2013); Fossi et al., (2017); Suaria and Aliani, (2014); Zeri et al., (2018); Ruiz-Oregon et al., (2018); Di-Meglio and Campana (2017); de Haan et al., (2019); Campana et al., (2018); Arcangeli et al., (2018); Palatinus et al., (2019); Arcangeli et al., (2015); Morris, (1980); Constantino et al., (2019); Aliani et al., (2003); Caldwell et al., (2019); de Haan et al., (2022); Pedrotti et al., (2022); Basurko et al., (2022); Marchetto et al., (2022); Collignon et al., (2014); EMODnet (2020).

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Figure 4.2.11. Boxplot (left) indicating the range, median and 25th/75th percentiles and Taylor diagram (right) of mean (2010-2014) macroplastics 5mm-2cm concentration (particles/Km²) from different simulations, against in-situ data (see Figure 4.2.10).

Figure 4.2.12. Mean (2010-2014) concentration (#/Km²) of macroplastics 5mm-2cm from different simulations, against available in situ data, averaged in different areas (Mediterranean, G. Lion, Ligurian Sea, Balearic Sea, Tyrrhenian Sea, Sicily strait, Ionian basin).

Figure 4.2.13. Boxplot (left) indicating the range, median and 25th/75th percentiles and Taylor diagram (right) of mean (2010-2014) macroplastics 2-20cm concentration (particles/Km²) from different simulations, against in-situ data.

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Figure 4.2.14. Mean (2010-2014) concentration (#/Km²) of macroplastics >20cm from different simulations, against available in situ data. In situ data were obtained from: Sanchez et al., (2013); Fossi et al., (2017); Suaria and Aliani, (2014); Zeri et al., (2018); Ruiz-Oregon et al., (2018); Di-Meglio and Campana (2017); de Haan et al., (2019); Campana et al., (2018); Arcangeli et al., (2018); Palatinus et al., (2019); Arcangeli et al., (2015); Morris, (1980); Constantino et al., (2019); Aliani et al., (2003); Jema et al., (2021); Garcia-Garin et al., (2020); EMODnet (2020).

Figure 4.2.15. Boxplot (left) indicating the range, median and 25th/75th percentiles and Taylor diagram (right) of mean (2010-2014) macroplastics >20 cm concentration (particles/Km²) from different simulations, against in-situ data (see Figure 4.2.14).

4.3 Microplastic dispersion in the *plasticparcels* model

4.3.1 Background

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The parcels Lagrangian framework provides a tool for advecting virtual particles using existing hydrodynamic model data. Virtual particles may represent anything that drifts in the ocean, such as water parcels, microplastic fragments, turtles, and even icebergs. It works by numerically integrating the hydrodynamic model velocity fields while including any additional particle-dependent physics and/or particle “behaviour”. Mathematically, particle trajectories are computed by solving the following equation:

$$x(t) = x(0) + \int_0^t v(x(s), s) + P(x(s), s) + B(x(s), s) ds,$$

where $x(t)$ describes the particle position at time t , $v = (u, v, w)$ is the hydrodynamic velocity field, P describes any particle-dependent physics (such as Stokes drift and wind-induced drift), and B describes any particle-specific behaviour (such as biofouling of microplastic).

The properties of plastic particles (e.g., size, shape, and density) determine what the dominant physical processes are at play, and due to the chaotic nature of the ocean, the dispersal patterns and transport behaviours of plastics will critically depend on their properties. Current state-of-the-art ocean models are either too coarse in resolution to capture these processes, or disregard these processes entirely, and so parameterising these processes is important to model and simulate their effects. The plasticparcels tool serves as an extension of the Parcels framework, in order to unify plastic dispersion modelling into one easy-to-use code. Plasticparcels contains parameterisations for physical processes such as Stokes drift, wind-induced drift and turbulent vertical mixing, as well as biological processes such as biofouling. While plasticparcels has been designed for researchers who routinely perform plastic particle dispersion simulations, it is equally useful to novice users who are new to Lagrangian ocean analysis techniques.

4.3.2 Theory

Here, we describe a few of the particle-dependent physics parameterisations and particle-specific behaviours.

Stokes drift - An important process that affects plastic particle dispersal in the upper ocean is the Stokes drift, whereby a particle subjected to a surface wave will experience a net displacement in the direction of wave propagation. We include a kernel to parameterise the effect of Stokes drift on a particle, based on the Phillips spectrum approximation developed in (Breivik et al., 2016). Specifically, we model this additional behaviour as P_{Stokes} , where the change in the particle position is described by:

$$P_{Stokes} = v_{Stokes}(x(t), t) = v_{Stokes}(x_{z=0}(t), t) \left(e^q - \beta \sqrt{-q\pi} \operatorname{erfc}(-q) \right),$$

Where z is the depth of the particle, $v_{Stokes}(x_{z=0}(t), t)$ is the surface Stokes drift velocity, $\beta = 1$ (as we assume a Phillips spectrum), and erfc is the complementary error function. Here, $q = 2k_p z$, and

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the peak wave number k_p is computed as $k_p = \frac{\omega_p^2}{9.81}$, where ω_p is the peak wave frequency $\omega_p = \frac{2\pi}{T_p}$, using the peak wave period $T_p = T_p(x_{z=0}(t), t)$.

Wind-induced drift - Plastic particles at the ocean surface that are not completely submersed will experience a force from the relative wind due to a wind drag, leading to a wind-induced drift. This wind-induced drift of the particle is called leeway (Allen et al., 1999), which can be decomposed into a downwind component (in the direction of the wind), and a crosswind component (which is typically non-zero for asymmetric objects). As we assume that each plastic particle is spherical, we can ignore the crosswind component of leeway, and only consider the downwind component of leeway. The downwind component follows an almost linear relationship with the relative 10m wind speed (Allen et al., 2005), so we model the leeway as

$$P_{Wind} = c \cdot (v_{Wind}(x(t), t) - v(x(t), t)),$$

where v_{Wind} is the wind velocity 10m above sea level, and c is the leeway rate (a percentage of wind speed, also known as the windage coefficient). Ignoring all additional behaviour of the particle, then $v_{Wind} - v$ is the relative wind acting on the particle.

Turbulent vertical mixing - An important process that is unresolved in even high-resolution ocean models is wind-driven turbulent mixing, which occurs at scales far smaller than a typical model ocean grid cell. In the vertical direction, this turbulent mixing can distribute even positively buoyant plastic particles throughout the mixed layer. To model this process, we take the approach of (Onink et al., 2022), by employing a Markov-0 styled stochastic parameterisation. Denote by $K_z = K_z(x(t))$ the vertical diffusion coefficient profile based on a K-profile parameterisation (KPP) model (Large et al., 1994). Then the displacement of a particle (in the vertical direction) with a settling velocity w can be modelled as an SDE (Grawe et al., 2012),

$$P_{Vertical\ Mixing} = \left(w + \frac{\partial K_z}{\partial z} \right) dt + \sqrt{2K_z} dW(t),$$

where $dW(t)$ is a Wiener noise increment with zero mean and a variance of dt . In our case, the displacement due to the settling velocity of a particle is already accounted for in the biofouling kernel, hence we only model the stochastic term (by setting $w = 0$). To numerically solve this equation, we use the stochastic generalisation of the Euler-Forward scheme, called the Euler-Maruyama scheme (Maruyama, 1955).

Biofouling - Plastic particles in the ocean can be a hotbed for the accumulation and growth of organisms, known as biofouling. The formation of a biofilm on the surface of a plastic particle can result in a density change, affecting the buoyancy of the particle. An initially buoyant particle may become negatively buoyant, and sink or settle, depending on the surrounding seawater density. We model the biofouling of a plastic particle following the approach of (Kooi et al., 2017), where the

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settling velocity of a particle is computed from the relative density difference of the plastic particle and the surrounding seawater. Here, we assume the biofilm growth (and decay) is primarily microbial algae, and is distributed homogeneously over the particle surface. The density of the biofouled plastic particle depends on the radius and density of the particle, and the thickness and density of the algal biofilm. The primary component of the biofouling kernel is modelling the change in the number of attached algae (denoted by A) on the surface of the plastic particle. As in (Kooi et al., 2017), we model the attached algal growth as

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = \frac{A_A \beta_A}{\theta_{Plastic}} + \mu_A A - m_A A - Q_{10}^{\frac{(T-20)}{10}} R_{20} A.$$

The first term models growth of algae due to collisions of the particle with algae in the surrounding seawater, where A_A is the ambient algal amount, β_A is the encounter kernel rate, and $\theta_{Plastic}$ is the surface area of the plastic particle. The second term models the growth of the biofilm, where the growth term μ_A is computed from the total productivity provided by biogeochemical model output. The third and fourth terms model the (grazing) mortality and respiration of the biofilm respectively. As in (Kooi et al., 2017), we use the constant mortality m_A and respiration R_{20} rates, with a temperature dependent term, $Q_{10}^{\frac{(T-20)}{10}}$, included in the respiration component.

The modelled attached algal growth, described above, drives a change in the buoyancy of the plastic particle, hence driving a change in its settling velocity. As per (Kooi et al., 2017), we use a settling velocity calculated using a modification of the Stokes equation, provided by (Dietrich 1982).

4.3.3 Implementation

Numerically, we solve the particle trajectory equation described in section 4.3.1 using a time-stepping approach, where we compute the displacements in the particle position as

$$\frac{dx(t)}{dt} = v(x(t), t) + P(x(t), t) + B(x(t), t),$$

updating the particle position at each timestep. As the relevant hydrodynamic, wind, wave, and biogeochemical model data exists on different spatial grids at different temporal resolutions, we compute the displacements caused by the hydrodynamic velocity fields, by the particle-dependent physics, and by the particle-specific behaviours separately, and combine at the end of each timestep in order to compute a net-displacement per particle.

We use a fourth-order Runge-Kutta scheme for the advection of each particle by the hydrodynamic velocity fields, and an Euler-Forward scheme for the displacements of each particle by additional processes.

In addition to the fine-scale physics parameterisations, plasticparcels provides global particle initialisation maps that represent best estimates for plastic pollution emissions along coastlines (Jambeck et al., 2015), from river sources (Meijer et al., 2021), and in the open-ocean from fishing-

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related activities (Kroodsma et al., 2018), as well as a current best estimate of buoyant plastic concentrations globally (Kaandorp et al., 2023). These maps are visualised in the figure below.

Figure 4.3.1 - Particle initialisations maps based on a) coastal mismanaged plastic waste emissions (Jambeck et al., 2015), b) riverine mismanaged plastic waste emissions (Meijer et al., 2021), c) fishing activity related plastic emissions (Kroodsma et al., 2018), and d) a current global surface concentration estimate (Kaandorp et al., 2023).

4.3.4 Validation

As yet, no specific validation of the produced datasets has been conducted as part of the NECCTON project. However, the particle initialisation maps have been derived from peer reviewed journal articles (Jambeck et al., 2015, Meijer et al., 2021, Kroodsma et al., 2018, and Kaandorp et al., 2023). While no specific validation was performed, the simulations run using plasticparcels as part of the NECCTON project closely align to the simulations performed in Kaandorp et al., 2023, which were compared to observational data with good results.

Earlier iterations of the physics kernels, utilised in the plasticparcels model, have been used in a number of published journal articles. The turbulent vertical mixing kernel, originally developed in Onink et al., 2022, and used along with the Stokes drift kernel, was validated by comparing vertical concentration profiles of simulated microplastics to field measurements of microplastic particles in the near-surface and mixed-layer, with reasonable results. Other versions of the Stokes drift kernel have been used in Kaandorp et al., 2020 and Onink et al., 2022, validated against open-ocean plastic concentration measurements in the Mediterranean, and Onink et al., 2021, validated against coastline plastic concentrations measurements. The wind-induced drift kernel was used in Manral et al., 2024, in order to model the drift of cold-stunned Kemp's ridley turtles stranding on the Dutch coast, with results validated against relevant stranding data. The biofouling kernel was originally developed in Lobelle et al., 2021, and later extended in Fischer et al., 2022, and Kaandorp et al., 2023, where the results have been validated against.

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5. Persistent Organic Pollutants

5.1 Introduction

The study on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) in marine environments is crucial due to their long-lasting presence, bioaccumulation potential, and adverse ecological effects. This section outlines the significance of key developments in marine POP chemistry, highlighting why specific pollutants and transformation processes have been selected for investigation. These advancements support various environmental assessment models and regulatory frameworks, aiding in the evaluation of pollution mitigation strategies. The research primarily focuses on regions where these pollutants are actively monitored and where their environmental behavior is of particular concern. By integrating new chemical mechanisms into modeling approaches, this work enhances predictive capabilities for POP fate under evolving environmental conditions. The code for this model can be found on GitHub at <https://github.com/jbieser/POPCYCLE>.

5.2 Implementation of marine POP chemistry

5.2.1 Background

We decided to focus on 3 specific groups of industrial POPs: Polychlorinated Biphenyls (PCB), Poly Brominated Diphenyl Ethers (PBDE) and Per- and Poly Fluoro Alkyl Substances (PFAS) (Figures 5.2.1-3). These pollutants have been earmarked for elimination by the Stockholm Convention. While PCBs were among the initial POPs classified by the SC, PBDEs and PFAS fall under the category of "new POPs" as designated by the convention [SC, 2019].

Two of the chosen pollutant categories exhibit hydrophobic characteristics. Both PCBs and PBDEs demonstrate extremely low solubility in water. On the other hand, PFAS possess a surfactant nature—featuring one hydrophobic head and one water-soluble head. Consequently, apart from sharing physical properties with PCBs and PBDEs, PFAS possess unique attributes that influence their behavior in the water column. All these contaminant classes can exist in a free dissolved state but exhibit a strong affinity for binding to organic carbon [Schwarzenbach et al. 2016, Mackay et al., 2006, Beyer and Biziuk, 2009].

In shelf waters, the concentration of recently released ("fresh") POPs tends to be higher compared to the open ocean, primarily due to their proximity to land-based sources. The absence of organic matter and degradation sources allows these chemicals to persist in the open ocean. Coastal waters serve as the initial phase of the journey for selected POPs from land to the open ocean [Hemond and Fechner, 2015, Mackay et al., 2006, Olenycz et al., 2015, Schwarzenbach et al., 2016]. A comprehensive understanding of their behavior in these regions is crucial for predicting their environmental fate under changing external conditions, such as variations in emissions and climate change.

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Figure 5.2.1: General chemical structure of chlorinated biphenyls (PCBs)

Figure 5.2.2: General structure of Polybrominated Biphenyl Ethers (PBDEs)

Figure 5.2.3: General chemical structure of Per- and Poly Fluoro Alkyl Substances (PFAS)

5.2.2. Theory

PCBs and PBDEs are hydrophobic POPs and share similar mechanisms of chemical transformation within environmental matrices. Conversely, PFAS function as surfactants, and their chemical properties dictate distinct behaviors in the marine environment compared to the other two classes of pollutants. Initially, we will examine the chemical processes common to PCBs and PBDEs.

Photolytic processes

The persistent nature of POPs determines their long half-life and tendency to accumulate over time in various matrices, including sediment, water and living organisms. Nonetheless, two prominent factors shape the fate of these pollutants in the environment: sunlight and bacterial activity. These elements enable POPs to undergo transformations under specific conditions, gradually leading to their degradation over time. It's important to emphasize that these "degradation pathways" do not unfold rapidly; instead, they facilitate the gradual removal of pollutants from the environment.

In aquatic environments, photolysis unfolds through two primary pathways: direct and indirect [Schwarzenbach et al., 2016]. Direct photolysis involves photons directly exciting pollutant molecules. However, this pathway is subject to several limiting factors, including water extinction, irradiation

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intensity, pollutant concentration, and the quantum yield of each step [Schwarzenbach et al., 2016]. Indirect photolysis constitutes a multifaceted process wherein photon energy is transferred to other constituents within the system rather than directly to the pollutant molecule [Schwarzenbach et al., 2016]. In the aqueous environment, the primary species involved in indirect photolysis include dissolved organic matter (DOM), $N O_3$, and $N O_2$ (hereafter referred to as ES -excited states) [Schwarzenbach et al., 2016, Bodrato and Vione, 2013]. Notably, indirect photolysis can generate radicals, which are atoms, molecules, or ions possessing at least one unpaired valence electron, within the aquatic environment. In the water column, transient species such as $OH\cdot$, $CO_3^{\cdot-}$, 1O_2 , and the triplet states of chromophoric dissolved organic matter, C-DOM^{*}, are present, playing a crucial role in the energy transfer of photoreactive species [Bodrato and Vione, 2013].

The energy received can either be transferred to pollutants or quenched by other biogeochemical species [Schwarzenbach et al., 2016]. Although the quenching process diminishes a considerable portion of the energy transmitted to POPs from ES, overall, this process holds significant importance [Bodrato and Vione, 2013, Schwarzenbach et al., 2016]. Firstly, the total concentration of ES surpasses that of POPs, resulting in a greater accumulation of photolytic fluxes within the system. Secondly, in heavily turbid waters where direct photolysis is improbable, the utilization of ES can still facilitate the transformation of POPs through indirect photolysis [Schwarzenbach et al., 2016].

When a POP molecule becomes excited, it can undergo various transformations. The direction of the photolytic reaction is influenced by the structural characteristics of each congener [Pagni and Sigman, 1999, Eriksson et al., 2004, Schwarzenbach et al., 2016]. Each specific congener within each class has a different molar attenuation coefficient (ϵ), which measures how strongly a chemical species absorbs and attenuates light at a given wavelength. As a general pattern, highly substituted pollutants from the PCB and PBDE classes are more likely to absorb more energy and undergo further changes in their chemical structure [Eriksson et al., 2004, Wong and Wong, 2006]. The detailed description of the implemented processes concerning photolytic transformations is presented in Section 5.2.3 The current section focuses on various pathways of chemical transformation and the resulting compounds.

Dechlorination/debromination

The initial photolytic transformation observed in POPs involves sequential dehalogenation, a process evident in both PCBs [Pagni and Sigman, 1999, Wong and Wong, 2006] and PBDEs [Eriksson et al., 2004, Pan et al., 2016]. When higher substituted congeners absorb UV light, they enter an excited state (as depicted in Figure 5.3.1). The absorbed energy subsequently breaks the weakest halogen bonds within the structure, leading to the dispersion of residual energy throughout the phenyl structure. This results in the creation of a radical molecule with an unpaired valence electron on the carbon atom, capable of further halogen loss until it attains a stable congener form. Following a series of such transformations, PCB153 (HSC) is transformed into PCB28 (LSC) as outlined in [Wong and Wong, 2006]. The LSC molecule exhibits a lower propensity for photon absorption, with its quantum yield of dechlorination being insignificant, rendering it relatively unaffected by solar irradiation.

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A similar transformational pathway is observed in the conversion of PBDEs [Eriksson et al., 2004, Wong and Wong, 2006]. Research by Pan et al [Pan et al., 2016] has established that HSC BDE209 undergoes conversion into LSC BDE47 through a comparable series of transformations (as illustrated in Figure 6). Consequently, the concentration of HSC decreases while the abundance of LSC in the system increases, both in the cases of PCBs and PBDEs. In the current study, photolytic dehalogenation contributes to the rising concentrations of LSC PCB28 and BDE47.

Figure 5.3.1 Main pathways of direct photolysis for PBDE (A) and PCB (B) in dissolved phase. An example of BDE209 chemical transformations in surface waters.

Hydroxylation

Hydroxylation, the second type of photolytic reaction, is observed in both PCB and PBDE pollutants [Zhao et al., 2015, Tehrani and Van Aken, 2014]. This process initiates with a similar excitation and radical formation as seen in the previous stage. However, the presence of hydroxyl radical OH is necessary, which is generated through indirect photolysis. Subsequently, in the ensuing phase of the reaction, both the molecule and hydroxyl radicals combine to produce a new category of pollutant - PCB-OH and PBDE-OH. In the final product, the halogen atom positioned in the ortho-position to the carbon-oxygen bond is substituted by a hydroxyl group OH (refer to Figure 5.3.1). Although the concentration of the product is relatively low, its presence in the aquatic environment is crucial to acknowledge. These new products demonstrate high bioconcentration factors (BCF) and low LC50 values. Notably, PBDE-OH significantly impacts the development of early-stage larvae, leading to a considerable decrease in hatching, as evidenced in studies involving zebrafish [Usenko et al., 2012]. Additionally, it is important to highlight that these pollutants have never been industrially manufactured; their presence in aquatic environments solely arises from photolytic hydroxylation. Consequently, PCB-OH and PBDE-OH are obtained as derivative products from this reaction. Both are included as side products in the current research.

Cyclisation

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Another potential pathway for phototransformation involves the production of furans. The chemical structure of PBDE exhibits greater flexibility compared to PCB due to the presence of an oxygen atom linking two phenyl rings [Wang et al., 2018]. This flexibility allows for the inclusion of larger bromine atoms in PBDE's structure, unlike the smaller chlorine atoms found in PCB [Wang et al., 2018, Rayne et al., 2006]. However, this flexibility also results in a wider range of possible products of photolysis [Eriksson et al., 2004]. In this process, a PBDE molecule in its radical form can detach another bromine in the ortho position close to the radical formation, leading to the formation of another cycle (refer to Figure 5.3.1)). Although the quantum yield for this process tends to be low, similar to the previous case [Eriksson et al., 2004], the toxicity and bioconcentration factors (BCF) of furans exceed those of the parent pollutant as well as PBDE-OH [Fernandes and Falandysz, 2020].

Photolysis of PFAS

PFAS, often dubbed "forever chemicals", are notorious for their extreme persistence in the environment. Few processes have demonstrated the ability to degrade or transform them. However, recent research suggests that, like PCBs and PBDEs, PFAS can undergo changes when exposed to UV light. Presently, there are two primary phototransformation pathways identified for PFAS. One potential degradation pathway for PFOA, known as photolytic chain shortening, has been observed [Giri et al., 2011], [Xin et al., 2023]. This process predominantly occurs in the atmosphere but can also manifest in aquatic environments, albeit with a lower quantum yield. Through this pathway, the parent pollutant transforms into another PFAS compound with a shorter carbon chain. Additionally, PFOA can undergo defluorination, losing fluorine atoms from its structure under UV irradiation [Xin et al., 2023]. For PFOA, the ratio of these two reactions is approximately 50/50. In both cases, the concentration of the parent PFOA decreases in its original environment.

Here, the transformation of PFOA is conceptualized as degradation without the production of daughter pollutants. This approach is adopted due to the complexity of simulating the specific pathways involved. Particularly relevant is the presence of iron, which plays a crucial role in simulating Fenton reactions [Schlesinger et al., 2022], leading to the production of hydroxyl radicals (OH•). These reactions significantly influence the direction of the photolytic degradation of PFOA. As a result, in this study, PFOA is impacted by UV irradiation, leading to a decrease in its concentration.

Biological transformation

As mentioned above, the interactions between POPs and living organisms are extremely complex and depend on a wide range of parameters. Biological degradation is no exception. This process depends not only on the structure of the pollutant, but is also strongly determined by the type of bacterial community and the chemical composition of the environment, in particular the oxygen content [Borja et al., 2005]. In the presence of oxygen, some microbial communities are able to break the structure of POP molecules (oxidative degradation) [Schwarzenbach et al., 2016, Alava et al., 2018, Borja et al., 2005]. This process is controlled not only by the class of aerobic bacteria but also by the stereochemical structure of the POP molecule and its affinity for the exact type of enzyme [Borja et al., 2005]. Boyle et al. show in their study that for most aerobic bacteria the oxidative ring cleavage mechanism (ORCM) takes place [Boyle et al., 1992]. In this case, PCB degradation by the bphA enzyme

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is only possible if the PCB has no substitutional chlorine in both ortho and meta positions on the same side of a ring (e.g. PCB28) (Figure 5.4.1).

Figure 5.3.2: Availability of different PCBs chemical structure for aerobic biodegradation.

This means that aerobic bacterial degradation will have an effect on the concentration of such PCB congeners as PCB28. However, the congener PCB153 chosen for the current simulations does not have a suitable structure for this process and aerobic biodegradation is not applicable in this case. However, in more recent study, Zhang and colleagues demonstrated that the cyanobacterium *Anabaena* PD-1 can degrade PCB153, at a lesser extent compared to PCB28 [Zhang et al., 2015]. Hence, the model incorporates biological degradation for all POPs, with higher extent for LSCs.

At the same time, there is another process of biological transformation in the marine environment. This process can be called biological dehalogenation rather than degradation. Without the presence of oxygen, other microbial communities can also degrade PCBs, although by the completely different mechanism of reductive dechlorination [Borja et al., 2005]:

In this case, PCBs are transformed into a lower chlorinated pollutant, but remain in the environment. This pathway occurs mainly under anaerobic conditions, such as in sediments or hypoxic waters [Borja et al., 2005]

5.2.3 Implementation

Five different pollutants from three POP classes have been represented: two congeners from the PCB class, two congeners from the PBDE class, and PFOA from the PFAS class (see Figure 5.4.2). Specifically, for the PCB and PBDE classes, we selected one higher substituted congener (HSC) each - PCB153 and BDE209. These chemicals exhibit very low water solubility and a high affinity for partitioning with organic matter. Moreover, they demonstrate a propensity for photolytic dechlorination [Pagni and Sigman, 1999, Wong and Wong, 2006] and are not readily available for aerobic bacterial degradation due to their structural characteristics. Alongside the HSCs, we simulated the fate of the lower substituted congeners (LSC) - PCB28 and BDE47. While these chemicals also possess low water solubility and a high affinity for organic matter, they are considered relatively more stable for phototransformation but are susceptible to biological degradation.

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Furthermore, the HSCs undergo transformation into LSCs through the processes of photolytic dechlorination and debromination. Consequently, a reduction in HSC concentration leads to an increase in LSC concentration within the water column. The chosen PCBs are prevalent in the environment, and comprehensive data required for simulations are readily accessible. Conversely, PBDEs pose a greater challenge for measurement due to their complexity and expense, yet extensive research has been conducted on their chemical transformations in the environment [Roszko et al., 2015, Zhao et al., 2015, Pan et al., 2016].

PFOA has been selected as an exemplar of POPs with a distinct set of properties owing to its unique structural characteristics. The rationale behind this selection has been extensively expounded upon in Section 5.2.1

Figure 5.4.1: Newly implemented POP congeners: a - BDE class; b - PCB class; c - PFAS class

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Figure 5.4.2: Newly implemented processes of POP transformation. Arrows: green – input; yellow – phase transformation; blue - diffusive exchange; red – removing of pollutants from the system.

Partitioning

We employ the concept of sorption rates (k_{sorp} and k_{desorp}). The concentration of pollutants bound to particulate organic matter (POP_{POM}) is calculated using the following equation 5.4.1

$$\frac{d[POP_{POM}]}{dt} = -(k_{desorp1} + k_{rem1})[POP_{POM}] - (k_{bur} + k_{sed})[POP_{POM}] + k_{sorp1}[POM][POP_{free}] + k_{resusp}[POP_{sed}]$$

Eq. 5.4.1

	PCB_{153}	PCB_{28}	BDE_{209}	BDE_{47}	PFOA
POM	0.01064 ²	0.0095 ^{1 2}	0.012 ^{1 3}	0.0086 ³	0.0024 ⁴
DOM	0.007 ¹	0.015 ¹	0.008 ¹	0.015 ¹	0.0026 ¹

Table 5.4.1: Rate constants describing process of PCB_{153} sorption on organic matrices. 1) Estimated 2) Calculated from Van Noort et al. [van Noort et al., 2003] 3) Calculated or estimated from Yan et al. [Yan et al., 2016] 4) Calculated from Fagbayigbo et al. [Fagbayigbo et al., 2021]

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Photolytic degradation

We utilize a hybrid approach, incorporating methodologies proposed by Schwarzenbach [Schwarzenbach et al., 2016] and Vione [Calza and Vione, 2015] for direct photolysis analysis. We derive a parameter for the kinetic rate of degradation of the targeted POP by considering factors such as photon flux (F_{POP}) and the quantum yield of the reaction (Q):

$$k_{photo} = Q \cdot F_{POP}$$

The photon flux absorbed by a pollutant is calculated from the irradiance across various wavelengths within the UV spectrum:

$$F_{POP} = E_{QF} \cdot \left[\frac{\epsilon(\lambda)[POP_{free}]}{EXT_{TOT}} \right]$$

E_{QF} – photon flux [$\mu\text{mol}/(\text{m}^2\text{s}) = \mu\text{E}$];

ϵ – extinction coefficient for specific POP [m^2/mol];

EXT_{TOT} – total extinction, includes marine water, DOM, detritus and phytoplankton [m^2/mol].

where E_{QF} represents photon flux (in $\mu\text{mol}/(\text{m}^2\text{s})$), calculated according to:

$$E_{QF} = \frac{N_p}{N_A \cdot 10^{-6}} = \frac{I[\text{Js}^{-1}\text{m}^{-2}] \cdot \lambda \cdot 10^{-9}[\text{ms}]}{h[\text{Js}] \cdot c[\text{ms}^{-1}] \cdot L[\text{mol}^{-1}] \cdot 10^{-6}} = \lambda 10.836 \cdot 10^{-2} [\mu\text{molm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}]$$

Biological degradation

Incorporating biological degradation into the model necessitates not only data on various bacterial communities and their concentrations in the water column, but also insights into the bioavailability of POPs. However, the specific mechanisms governing these processes remain hypothetical, as the kinetic and thermodynamic parameters are yet to be determined. Moreover, the current version of the ECOSMO biogeochemical model does not explicitly account for bacterial communities, requiring simplifications in the model implementation. To address these challenges, we have introduced a generalized process of biodegradation, devoid of specificity regarding bacterial communities. Instead, we parameterize this process based on remineralization rates:

$$k_{bio} = K_{BIO} \left(2 \cdot 10^{-8} \left(1 + 20 \left(\frac{T^2}{132 + T^2} \right) \right) (10[DOM] + [POM]) \right)$$

T - temperature [K];

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KBIO - parameterisation coefficient [-].

Finally, a biological degradation rate in sediments is implemented as a constant for all POPs and equal to $3.935 \times 10^{-10} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [Davis, 2004]

5.3 Validation

The validation of this model is still ongoing.

6. Persistent Organic Pollutants Global atmospheric transport model

6.1 Introduction

The modeling of legacy persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and emerging organic contaminants (EOCs), such as organophosphate flame retardants (OPFRs), in the global ocean, particularly the Arctic, is a critical topic of environmental science (Xie et al., 2020). Legacy POPs, including polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethanes (DDTs), have been extensively studied due to their persistence, bioaccumulation, and long-range transport capabilities. Emerging contaminants like OPFRs, used as flame retardants and plasticizers, are increasingly detected in marine environments, raising concerns about their environmental fate and ecological impacts (Xie et al., 2022).

The Arctic Ocean, despite its remote location, is a significant sink for these contaminants due to global atmospheric and oceanic transport processes. The cold condensation effect and bioaccumulation in Arctic food webs exacerbate the risks to indigenous communities and wildlife. Modeling these contaminants involves understanding their sources, transport pathways, degradation rates, and interactions with marine ecosystems. Advanced models integrate physicochemical properties, environmental parameters, and global circulation patterns to predict their distribution and behavior (Wania and Mackay, 1995). Recent studies have highlighted the importance of multi-compartment models that consider air-water exchange, particle settling, and biogeochemical processes (Wania and Mackay, 1995). For instance, Ma et al. (2024) used CanMETOP, a coupled atmosphere-ocean model to assess the fate of OPFRs in global ocean, revealing significant seasonal variations in concentrations.

6.2 Canadian Model for Environmental Transport of Organochlorine Pesticides (CanMETOP)

6.2.1 Background

The Canadian Model for Environmental Transport of Organochlorine Pesticides (CanMETOP) is a multimedia fate and transport model designed to simulate the environmental behavior of organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) on a global scale. It employs a fugacity-based approach to predict the partitioning, transport, and degradation of chemicals across environmental compartments, including air, water, soil, and biota (McDonald et al., 2000).

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CanMETOP is also well-suited for modelling emerging contaminants such as OPFRs in the global ocean (Ma et al., 2024). OPFRs, widely used as flame retardants and plasticizers, share similar properties with legacy POPs, including volatility, persistence, and potential for long-range transport (Xie, 2022). CanMETOP's adaptable framework can be tailored to simulate OPFRs by incorporating their specific physicochemical properties, degradation rates, and emission scenarios. Its ability to model multi-compartment interactions and global transport pathways makes it a valuable tool for assessing the fate of OPFRs in marine environments, particularly in sensitive regions like the Arctic, where cold condensation and bioaccumulation are significant concerns. The code for this model can be found on zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11214066>.

6.2.2. Theory

The CanMETOP is grounded in the fugacity-based modeling approach, (Harner et al., 2001) which quantifies the tendency of a chemical to escape from one environmental compartment to another. Multimedia fugacity models have been used widely in modeling regional and global distributions of persistent organic chemicals (Mackay, 1991; Wania and Mackay, 1995; Koprivnjak and Poissant, 1997). This theoretical framework allows CanMETOP to simulate the partitioning, transport, and transformation of OCPs across global environmental media, including air, water, soil, and biota. The model incorporates key processes such as advection, diffusion, degradation, and intermedia exchange, enabling it to predict the long-range transport and accumulation of POPs in remote regions like the Arctic. CanMETOP also integrates climatic and oceanic data, making it highly adaptable for studying the spatial and temporal distribution of contaminants. Its theoretical foundation in fugacity and its ability to account for multi-compartment interactions make it a robust tool for understanding the environmental fate of chemicals on a global scale.

6.2 Implementation

The CanMETOP is utilized to simulate the global distribution of OPFRs in the atmosphere and seawater (Ma et al., 2024). The model operates at a horizontal resolution of 1°×1° latitude/longitude and a temporal resolution of 20 minutes, with 14 vertical levels (0, 1.5, 3.9, 10, 350, 700, 1200, 2000, 3000, 5000, 7000, 9000, and 11000 m) following a terrain-following coordinate system. Meteorological data, including wind, temperature, and precipitation, are sourced from the National Centers for Environmental Prediction (NCEP) (<http://dss.ucar.edu/datasets/ds083.2/>), while geographical data such as terrain elevation and land use are obtained from the Oak Ridge National Laboratory. To enhance its applicability for OPFRs in marine environments, a water-sediment module, based on a mass balance model, has been integrated into CanMETOP, enabling the investigation of OPFR behavior in oceanic systems. This adaptation underscores the model's versatility and robustness in simulating the environmental fate of emerging contaminants. The molecular formulas and abbreviations of these OPFRs congeners are documented and presented in Table 6.1.

The spatial distribution of annually averaged OPFRs concentrations in the atmosphere at 1.5m above ground in 2020, as shown in Figs. 6.2.1.a and 6.2.1.b, reveals higher concentrations in regions with intense industrial activity and population density, such as East Asia (eastern China, Japan, South Korea), India, Western Europe, and the US. The global mean atmospheric concentration in 2020 was

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875 pg/m³ (95% CI: 762–1024 pg/m³). Long-range atmospheric transport significantly influences regions with low emissions, such as Mongolia, where concentrations reached 138 pg/m³ despite contributing only 0.008% of global emissions. Similarly, African countries were affected by high-emission nations like Nigeria and the Democratic Republic of Congo, while Brazil and Mexico contributed to elevated OPFR levels in South and Central America. This transport mechanism also explains the presence of OPFRs in the pristine Arctic, likely originating from distant sources.

In seawater, OPFR contamination is driven by atmospheric deposition (dry/wet), air-water gaseous exchange, and surface runoff, although CanMETOP excludes the latter. The modeled global mean seawater concentration in 2020 was 0.79 ng/L (95% CI: 0.56–1.10 ng/L). Higher concentrations were observed in coastal regions, particularly near eastern China, South Korea, Japan, Western Europe, and the eastern US, underscoring the importance of proximity to land-based sources in shaping OPFR distribution in marine environments. These findings highlight the role of atmospheric transport and deposition in disseminating OPFRs globally, even to remote regions like the Arctic.

6.3 Uncertainties

The primary sources of uncertainty in CanMETOP-modeled concentrations stem from the emission inventory and physicochemical properties of OPFRs. These uncertainties are analyzed in detail (Ma et al., 2024). Given the model's incorporation of complex dynamics—such as dry and wet deposition, precipitation scavenging, advection (horizontal and vertical), and turbulent diffusion—a first-order error propagation method is used to evaluate sensitivity and uncertainty. This approach quantifies how variations in input parameters affect model outputs, ensuring robust assessments of OPFRs behavior in the environment. Such uncertainty analysis is critical for improving the reliability of CanMETOP predictions and informing risk assessments for emerging contaminants.

Table 6.3.1 Names, abbreviations, formulae, and physical-chemical properties of OPFRs (Ma et al., 2024)

Acronym	Name	CAS	Formula	Solubility (mg/L) 25°C	Log K _{ow}	log K _{oc}	log K _{oa}	Vapor pressure (mmHg) (25 °C)	Henry's law constant (atm/m ³ /mol) (25°C)	Half-life (medium)	BCF
TEP	Triethyl phosphate	78-40-0	C ₆ H ₁₅ O ₄ P	5.0×10 ⁵	0.8	1.86	6.63	0.29	3.5×10 ⁻⁶	-	3.2
TPP	Tripropyl phosphate	513-08-6	C ₉ H ₂₁ O ₄ P	8.3×10 ²	2.67		6.42	2.9×10 ⁻²	8.2×10 ⁻⁶	-	0.9
TIBP	Tri-iso-butyl phosphate	126-71-6	C ₁₂ H ₂₇ O ₄ P	3.7	3.6		7.48	1.3×10 ⁻²	1.1×10 ⁻⁴	4.3 h (atmosphere)	19.5
TNBP	Tri-n-butyl phosphate	126-73-8	C ₁₂ H ₂₇ O ₄ P	2.8×10 ²	4	2.83	9.21	1.1×10 ⁻³	1.5×10 ⁻⁷	<1 h (atmosphere)	39.8
TCEP	Tris(2-chloroethyl) phosphate	115-96-8	C ₆ H ₁₂ Cl ₃ O ₄ P	7.0×10 ³	1.44	3.05	7.42	1.1×10 ⁻⁴	3.3×10 ⁻⁶	17.5 h (atmosphere)	0.4
TCPP	Tris(iso-propyl) phosphate	13674-84-5	C ₉ H ₁₈ Cl ₃ O ₄ P	1.6×10 ³	2.59	2.71	8.2	1.9×10 ⁻⁶	6.0×10 ⁻⁸	8.6 h (atmosphere)	3.3
TBEP	Tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate	78-51-3	C ₁₈ H ₃₉ O ₇ P	1.2×10 ³	3.65	4.83	13	2.1×10 ⁻⁷	3.3×10 ⁻¹¹	3 h (atmosphere)	25.6
TDCPP	Tris(1,3-dichloroisopropyl) phosphate	13674-87-8	C ₉ H ₁₅ Cl ₆ O ₄ P	1.5	3.8	2.35	10.6	7.4×10 ⁻⁸	2.6×10 ⁻⁹	21.3 h (atmosphere)	21.4

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TPP	Triphenyl phosphate	115-86-6	$C_{18}H_{15}O_4P$	1.9	4.59	3.72	8.45	1.2×10^{-6}	3.3×10^{-6}	50-60 d (pond hydrosol)	113
EHDPP	2-Ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate	1241-94-7	$C_{20}H_{27}O_4P$	1.9	5.37	4.21	8.92	6.5×10^{-7}	2.5×10^{-7}	-	855
TEHP	Tris(2-ethylhexyl) phosphate	78-42-2	$C_{24}H_{51}O_4P$	0.6	9.49	6.87	14.9	2.0×10^{-6}	9.6×10^{-5}	-	3.2
TMPP	Tris(methylphenyl) phosphate	78-32-0	$C_{21}H_{21}O_4P$	0.36	5.11	4.35	5.88	1.8×10^{-7}	9.2×10^{-7}	7.5 h (sewage sludge)	2543

Fig. 6.2.1 .a). CanMETOP modeled OPFR concentrations in air and seawaters in 2020. a. air (gas + particle phase, unit: pg/m³); b). seawater (unit: ng/L). (Ma et al., 2024)

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7. Mercury

7.1 Introduction

The biogeochemical cycle of mercury (Hg) has been altered for centuries due to anthropogenic activities and legacy Hg continues cycling through the biosphere through long range atmospheric transport, deposition to the ocean and land, and subsequent re-emissions. Thus, despite efforts to reduce primary emissions after the enforcement of the Minamata Convention, there are still concerns over wildlife and human exposure to Hg, particularly due to the production and bioaccumulation of the neurotoxic species methylmercury (MeHg) in the global ocean and other aquatic ecosystems (Médiéu et al., 2024, Tseng et al., 2021, Schartup et al., 2019). The assessment of the outcomes of the policies implemented following the Minamata Convention on the environmental fate of Hg and exposure concentrations is urgently needed (Dastoor et al., 2024, Selin et al., 2018; Sunderland & Selin, 2013).

Distribution of mercury species in seawater, LTL, and HTL at the global and regional scale will be provided as Mercury products for the Copernicus Marine System (see Table 1 in D8.1, Canu et al., 2024) from two coupled models (HAMSOM-ECOSMO-MERCY and OGSTM-BFM-Hg). The development of Mercury products stems from the recent development of high-resolution coupled hydrodynamic biogeochemical models for Hg fate and transport (Bieser et al., 2023, Rosati et al., 2022). The OGSTM-BFM-Hg model will be used to provide Mercury CMS products for the Mediterranean Sea, and the HAMSOM-ECOSMO-MERCY *model for the North Sea, Baltic Sea, and Mediterranean*. Key processes simulated in both models include *photochemical and biological transformations* that interlink the different Hg species, *partitioning* to particulate organic carbon and DOC, *gaseous exchange* of dissolved gaseous mercury with the atmosphere, *bioconcentration* in phytoplankton and *bioaccumulation* in zooplankton. The main difference between the two models is that the ICON-Hg model also includes *bioaccumulation in the HTL*, whereas the OGSTM-BFM-Hg has a higher number of plankton functional types compared to the former (Table 7.1).

Following the project commitment to open science principles, the codes of the two models for simulating mercury biogeochemistry are released as open-source programs available on GitHub through the NECCTON algorithm repository (<https://github.com/neccton-algo>). The OGSTM-BFM-Hg is now fully integrated into the repositories of the BFM consortium (<https://github.com/BFM-Community/BiogeochemicalFluxModel>) and of the OGSTM model (<https://github.com/inogs/ogstm>) under the branch 'neccton_WP8'. This achievement will allow a seamless merging of future developments made in the ecosystem (BFM) or transport (OGSTM) model into the coupled Hg model. The NECCTON project also supported improvements of the mercury modelling tools, which include: an improved parameterization for seawater-atmospheric exchange for both models following recommendations from the working group on “The Multi-Compartment Hg (mercury) Modeling and Analysis Project (MCHgMAP)” (Dastoor et al., 2024) (section 7.2), and the acquisition of improvements in biogeochemical processes from WP5 of NECCTON (Table 7.1), for the OGSTM-BFM-Hg model (sections 7.3 and 7.4) and HAMSOM-ECOSMO-MERCY *model* (section 7.5). The spatial resolution of the grid of the OGSTM-BFM-Hg model was improved from 1/16° horizontal resolution and 70 vertical

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levels to 1/24 horizontal resolution and 125 vertical levels (see Section 7.5.2). A one-year long test was run at the improved resolution, and the possibility to run the longer hindcast simulation at the higher spatial resolution will be tested in the next months.

Region	Model	Ecosystem module			Mercury module		
		PFTs	Organic Detritus	HTL	State variables **	Partition	Upgrades
MED	BFM-Hg	4 PHY, 4 ZOO, 1 BAC	2 POM, 3 DOM, 3CDOM*	no	4 Hg species + derived variables for partitioning to DOM and POM. + 8 bio- accumulation variables	Partitioning of HgII and MMHg to 2 classes of POM ***	air- seawater exchange of gaseous Hg Light and POM dynamics ***
NS/BS	ECOSMO -MERCY	3 PHY 2 ZOO 1 MAC	1 POM 1 DOM	2 Fish	10 Hg species + 26 bio- accumulation variables	Three-way partitioning between dissolved chlorine complex, DOM, and POM	air- seawater exchange of gaseous Hg air-sea exchange of DMHg
* see NECCTON Deliverable 5.2 ** State variables for mercury modules are described in detail in D8.1 *** WP5 Dependencies							

Table 7.1. Comparison of the main features of coupled transport-ecosystem-mercury model tools available in the NECCTON algorithm repository. Dependencies and other upgrade developed in the project are also shown.

7.2 Improvements in the seawater-atmospheric exchange of gaseous mercury

7.2.1 Background

The exchange of mercury between the ocean and the atmosphere plays an important role in the cycling of mercury in the global environment. According to current best knowledge of the global mercury cycle, the exchange of mercury between atmosphere and ocean is the largest gross flux in the environment. A major challenge is, that fluxes cannot be observed directly and need to be deduced from gradient measurements. Additionally, these observations are highly wind driven but can only be observed at relatively low wind speeds due to technical limitations. Thus, the way this process is parametrized is of utmost importance. Available parameterizations of mercury air-water exchange used in modelling and measurement studies still vary considerably indicating an incomplete understanding of the process and lack of direct measurements. We here present the parameterizations recommended for use.

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7.2.2. Theory

The two-layer (film) model by Liss and Slater (1974), which is the traditional parameterization used to determine the Hg air-water gas exchange flux is recommended. It is possible to neglect the gas-side part of the transfer velocity in the model as the gas-side conductance for Hg is much bigger than on the water-side ($k_w \ll k_a H'$) (Nerentorp Mastromonaco et al., 2017). We further recommend the parameterization of the gas transfer velocity (k_w) by Wanninkhof (2014) that is based on updated methodology of Wanninkhof (1992) and is in close agreement with parameterizations based on gas exchange process studies over the oceans (e.g. Nightingale et al., 2000a; 2000b) (Fig 7.2.1). Recent micrometeorological measurements by Osterwalder et al. (2021) provide estimates of k_w directly determined for Hg. However, this is the first time this method has been used for Hg flux evaluation and more measurements are needed to validate the result. Therefore, the application of this alternative parameterization is recommended only for the uncertainty analysis.

Fig. 7.2.1 - Wind speed dependence of air-water gas transfer velocities from various parameterizations often applied in Hg modelling and measurement studies scaled to a Schmidt number of 660 (CO_2 in seawater at 20°C). Nightingale et al. (2000a) parameterizations 1 and 2 (in solid dark blue) are both commonly used in Hg work and give almost identical results. The dark blue dotted line refers to Nightingale et al. (2000b), the orange line to Wanninkhof (1992), the green line to Wanninkhof (2014), the light blue line to Liss and Merlivat (1986), the yellow line to McGillis et al. (2001), and the pink line to Osterwalder et al. (2021).

The temperature dependence of the gas transfer velocity of Hg is defined by the Schmidt number of Hg (Schmidt number is a ratio of water kinematic viscosity to the diffusion coefficient of a gas). The biggest differences between available parametrizations for the Schmidt number of Hg relate to the diffusion coefficient of $\text{Hg}(0)$. For the diffusion coefficient of $\text{Hg}(0)$ in the baseline simulations, we recommend the newest experimentally determined approximation from Kuss (2014). An alternative for sensitivity tests is the widely used parameterisation by Wilke and Chang (1955), which provides

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higher values for the diffusion coefficient and consequently lower values for the Schmidt number (Fig. 7.2.1). Parameterizations of water kinematic viscosities by Kestin et al. (1978) and Sharqawy et al. (2010; fresh and saltwater versions) do not differ significantly from each other. Of the two available parameterisations of the water kinematic viscosity for seawater (Wanninkhof, 1992; Sharqawy et al., 2010), we suggest the latter to be more universal since it provides values for a wide range of salinity. Fig. 7.2.2 shows the temperature dependence on the transfer velocity for parameterizations recommended compared to the alternative combination.

Fig 7.2.2 - A) Temperature dependence of the Hg^0 diffusion coefficient. B) Temperature dependence of the Schmidt number of $Hg(0)$ in seawater (from Wilke and Chang (1955) in green, and Kuss (2014) in blue). C) Temperature dependence of air-seawater gas transfer velocity for $Hg(0)$ (from Wilke and Chang (1955) and Wanninkhof (2014) in green, from Kuss (2014) and Wanninkhof (2014) in blue).

Parameterization of $Hg(0)$ exchange flux between air and seawater ($S = 35$ g/kg) the following approach:

- $F_{Hg} = k_w (c_w - c_a / H')$ [$ng\ m^{-2}\ h^{-1}$]
 c_a and c_w are concentrations of $Hg(0)$ in air and water [$ng\ m^{-3}$].
- $H' = \exp(-2404.3/T + 6.92)$ (Andersson et al., 2008a)
 T is water temperature [K].
- $k_w = 0.251 U_{10}^2 \sqrt{Sc_{Hg} / 660} \times 10^{-2}$ [$m\ h^{-1}$] (Wanninkhof, 2014)
 U_{10} is wind speed at 10 m height [$m\ s^{-1}$].
- $Sc_{Hg} = v_{sw} / D_{sw}$, $v_{sw} = n_{sw} / \rho_{sw}$ (Sharqawy et al., 2010)
 $n_{sw} = n_{fw} (1.064 + 6.067 \times 10^{-4} t - 2.753 \times 10^{-6} t^2)$, [$g\ cm^{-1}\ s^{-1}$]
 $n_{fw} = 4.2844 \times 10^{-4} + (0.0157 (t + 64.993)^2 - 9.13)^{-1}$, [$g\ cm^{-1}\ s^{-1}$]
 $\rho_{sw} = 1.028 - 4.970 \times 10^{-5} t - 5.575 \times 10^{-6} t^2$, [$g\ cm^{-1}\ s^{-1}$]
 t is water temperature [$^{\circ}C$]
- $D_{sw} = 0.0011 \exp(-1330.2/T)$, [$cm^2\ s^{-1}$] (Kuss, 2014)
 T is water temperature [K].

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7.2.3 Implementation

We implemented the updated air-sea exchange parametrization into the MERCY model. Options are to use temporally high-resolution input data from a directly coupled atmospheric model or to read daily Hg concentration and deposition fields for the air-sea exchange. In case physical atmospheric boundary data is only available offline, we use the ERA5 reanalysis products. Here, besides the wind speed, also its variability over the time step can be considered as to not underestimate effective transfer velocities due to averaging of wind fields. Based on the parameterization of Hg₀ exchange, we also implemented the air-sea exchange of dimethyl mercury.

The code of the OGSTM-BFM-Hg model was improved to read spatially and temporally variable input files of atmospheric Hg₀ concentrations, which were hard-coded in the mercury gas exchange subroutine in the first model version. This improvement enables offline coupling with models that simulate the dynamics of Hg in the atmosphere (Travnikov et al., 2017) and thus represents a significant step towards multidisciplinary to improve modeling capabilities and perform intercomparisons (Dastoor et al., 2024).

7.3 WP5 Dependencies: POC dynamics of the coupled model OGSTM-BFM-Hg

7.3.1 Background

The fate and transport of mercury species in the marine environment is influenced by the dynamics of particulate organic matter (POM) that affect their vertical transport and availability for biological uptake and transformations (Lamborg et al., 2016). Moreover, microbial remineralization of POM and DOM is considered a key process linking the biogeochemical cycles of mercury and carbon (Cossa et al., 2022, Sunderland et al., 2009). The conversion of inorganic Hg into MeHg (i.e., Hg methylation) is performed by microbial taxa carrying specific genes (*HgcAB*) that are widespread in the global ocean, particularly in oxygenated subsurface waters (Villar et al., 2020). Organic matter degradation also results in the release of dissolved Hg previously associated with DOC and POC, which increase its bioavailability further favouring its conversion to MeHg. As a result, the vertical distribution of MeHg in the ocean is often characterized by a subsurface maximum in concentrations that falls within the zone of maximum apparent oxygen utilization and organic carbon remineralization, while geographical distributions seem to be governed by the intensity of primary production and, consequently, of the degradation of organic matter (e.g. Cossa et al., 2022; 2009; Sunderland et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2022).

7.3.2. Theory

Coupled models for Hg cycling assume that the methylation rate at a given point in time and space is proportional to the rate of organic carbon remineralization. One limitation of this approach is to assume a constant composition in taxa of the microbial community across time and space. However, at the state of the art there are not enough observational data to resolve the composition of the microbial community, nor a sufficient mechanistic understanding of Hg methylation. Thus, scaling Hg methylation rates to organic carbon remineralization rates offers a first approximation that empirically

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fits reasonably well to large-scale observational patterns of MeHg distribution both in the vertical and zonal/meridional dimensions (Bieser et al., 2023; Rosati et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022).

7.3.3 Implementation

The mercury module of the OGSTM-BFM-Hg model has been rewritten into the upgraded version of the OGSTM-BFM model developed by WP5 in NECCTON (D5.2) in its three-dimensional configuration.

One of the key developments made in WP5 for the BFM model is the differentiation between two classes of particulate organic detritus (POC) with different size and sinking velocities to improve the representation of POC sinking and remineralisation (see D5.2, section 7.2). Following these improvements, the mercury module has been modified to read two POC classes (S-POC for small POC and L-POC for large POC) rather than one, which are used in the calculation of Hg partitioning, and to take into account the rate of remineralization of the two POC classes for scaling the Hg methylation process. Furthermore, the simulation of mercury cycling is expected to benefit from the general improvement in simulating biogeochemical processes achieved in WP5.

The partitioning process, involving the two Hg species HgII and MMHg, is parameterized by calculating the fraction dissolved in the water ($f_{Hg_i_d}$) or associated with POC and DOC state variables. For a given species Hg_i , the equations read as follows:

$$f_{Hg_i_d} = \frac{1}{1 + K_{D\ Hg-DOC} \times C_{DOC} + K_{D\ Hg-POC} \times C_{S-POC} + K_{D\ Hg-POC} \times C_{L-POC}}$$

$$f_{Hg_i_{DOC}} = \frac{K_{D\ Hg-DOC} \times C_{DOC}}{1 + K_{D\ Hg-DOC} \times C_{DOC} + K_{D\ Hg-POC} \times C_{S-POC} + K_{D\ Hg-POC} \times C_{L-POC}}$$

$$f_{Hg_i_{S-POC}} = \frac{K_{D\ Hg-POC} \times C_{S-POC}}{1 + K_{D\ Hg-DOC} \times C_{DOC} + K_{D\ Hg-POC} \times C_{S-POC} + K_{D\ Hg-POC} \times C_{L-POC}}$$

$$f_{Hg_i_{L-POC}} = \frac{K_{D\ Hg-POC} \times C_{L-POC}}{1 + K_{D\ Hg-DOC} \times C_{DOC} + K_{D\ Hg-POC} \times C_{S-POC} + K_{D\ Hg-POC} \times C_{L-POC}}$$

The equation for mercury methylation has been modified to take into account the remineralization of both small and large POC:

$$k_{met} = x_{met} \cdot (rem_{S-POC} + rem_{L-POC})$$

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7.4 WP5 Dependencies: the bio-optical module of the coupled model OGSTM-BFM-Hg

7.4.1 Background

Solar radiation is an important controlling factor for mercury in the ocean that acts through direct and indirect effects. Photochemical reactions, which include redox transformations between HgII and Hg0 as well as the demethylation of MMHg and DMHg, promote a fast cycling of Hg species in surface waters (Luo et al., 2020). The concentration of dissolved gaseous mercury (DGM, the sum of Hg0 and DMHg) tend to increase during the day following irradiance course (e.g., Lanzillotta et al., 2002), resulting in over-saturation of the gas that leads to an outgassing flux into the atmosphere (Section 7.1). Indirect effects of light are those that affect the composition and functioning of the ecosystem (D5.2, Section 9) and thus, in turn, Hg dynamics.

Although a complete mechanistic understanding of photochemical reactions is still lacking, research clearly show the importance of UV light radiation and DOM, playing a central role in the photochemical degradation of MMHg (Gindorf et al. 2025) and in the redox transformations of inorganic Hg species in natural waters (Luo et al., 2020). At high DOM concentrations almost all UV radiation is lost due to light attenuation, however, at lower concentrations, DOM facilitates photochemical processes via an unknown mechanisms. On the other hand, the photochemical degradation of DMHg to MMHg seems to be unaffected by DOM (West et al., 2022). Therefore, coupling the mercury module with an advanced multispectral optical module (D5.2, Section 9) that also include new state variables for chromophoric DOM (cDOM) improve the capability of simulating Hg dynamics also enabling a smooth integration of new data from experimental studies in future investigations.

7.4.2. Theory

Photochemical transformations of Hg species are parameterized in the OGSTM-BFM-Hg model as described in Rosati et al., 2022. A scheme of the photochemical and biological reactions along with other key processes implemented in the model is shown in Figure 7.4.1. Each reaction is parameterized as a linear function of available shortwave radiation scaled with empirical coefficient obtained from field observations (Soerensen et al., 2010, Whalin et al., 2022).

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Figure 7.4.1. Hg dynamics in the coupled model OGSTM-BFM-Hg (Rosati et al., 2022). The Hg model simulates the cycling of inorganic (Hg^{II} and Hg^0) and methylated Hg species (MMHg and DMHg) resolving: the *partitioning* of Hg^{II} and MMHg between particulate (Hg_{POC} , $MMHg_{POC}$) and dissolved species (Hg_{Diss} , as Hg_{DOC} + $HgCl_n$, and $MMHg_{Diss}$, as $MMHg_{DOC}$ + $MMHgCl$) based on partition coefficients (K_D) and concentrations of POC and DOC, the *photochemical and biological transformations* (dotted colored arrows) as first order kinetics depending on the rate constants k_x , the *gaseous exchange of Hg^0* to the atmosphere controlled by wind speed through the volatilization rate constant k_{vol} , and the MMHg *bioaccumulation* (pink arrows) driven by phytoplankton uptake in 4 different PFTs and trophic transfer to 4 zooplankton PFTs.

7.4.3 Implementation

The mercury module of the OGSTM-BFM-Hg model has been rewritten into the upgraded version of the OGSTM-BFM model developed by WP5 in NECCON (D5.2) in its three-dimensional configuration.

7.5 Validation

7.5.1 HAMSOM-ECOSMO-MERCY model

We evaluated modelled concentrations of Hg species in water and their bio-accumulation in biota. Our model chain includes a global run based on the ICON-MERCY model followed by a regional nested run using the HAMSOM-ECOSMO-MERCY model setup for the North- and Baltic Seas. The global model is able to reproduce the pronounced observed latitudinal distribution of both total and gaseous mercury (Fig. 7.5.1). Based on this, we are confident using the global model to drive the regional setup. For this demonstration, we focused on the North Sea and Baltic Sea region. Here, we investigate the model capability to reproduce the general distribution of observed mercury levels with a focus on

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maximum and minimum values (Fig. 7.5.2). The model has a high skill in reproducing the observed distribution, albeit it underestimates observed peak values. These values are associated mostly with the Wadden Sea in the North Sea. We find that the source for the observed maxima is likely the process of resuspension at the coastline in the Wadden Sea. A process that would need higher model resolution to be resolved. At this point, we will exclude the coastal area behind the barrier islands from our model output to avoid these problems. Figure 7.5.3 shows that the model can reproduce the horizontal and vertical distribution of mercury. Especially in the Baltic Sea, the stratification above the deep central basins can be reproduced successfully.

Finally, we evaluate the modelled concentration and fraction of methylated mercury as well as the bio-accumulation to higher trophic levels. Table 7.5.1. shows that the model is actually capable to reproduce the mean observed concentrations in fish as well as the observed range.

Fig 7.5.1 - Global latitudinal distribution of total mercury (THg) and dissolved gaseous mercury (DGM) in the surface ocean. Note that DGM is the sum of elemental Hg^0 and gaseous dimethyl mercury. Given are also the mean values as constant lines.

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Fig 7.5.2 - Frequency distribution of observed (red) and modelled (blue) total mercury levels in the regional setup.

Hg species	Mean (10th–90th percentile)		Model error			Performance criteria		
	Observation	Model	Systematic	Random	Amplitude	FAC2	MQO	N
Hg _T	2.69 (0.9–6.0) pM	2.24 (1.1–3.7) pM	–17 %	67 %	–55 %	72 %	1.44	435
Hg ⁰	73.2 (53–99) fM	74.6 (52–123) fM	2 %	35 %	38 %	97 %	0.84	477
MeHg	190 (20–612) fM	135 (48–270) fM	–28 %	160 %	–74 %	49 %	0.80	264
MeHg / Hg _T	11.4 % (1.3 %–30 %)	9.9 % (3.6 %–20 %)	–5 %	190 %	–55 %	53 %	0.98	160
Hg in fish	28 (12–52) ng g ^{–1}	25 (6–71) ng g ^{–1}	3 %	n/a	9 %	n/a	n/a	1166

n/a: not applicable.

Table 7.5.1 - Statistical analysis of modelled mercury species including bio-accumulation to higher trophic levels.

Fig 7.5.3 - Map of total mercury concentrations in the North Sea and Baltic Sea with superimposed observations. Left side shows values for March and right side values for August. For three selected locations A, B, C, we also show vertical profiles.

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7.5.2 OGSTM-BFM-Hg model

An initial evaluation of the capability of OGSTM-BFM-Hg model to reproduce the observed spatial gradients of Hg species concentrations in the Mediterranean Sea is provided in Rosati et al., 2022. Here we compare model output of the first model version, running on a mesh with horizontal resolution of 1/16 (about 6 km), with output of the improved model running on a mesh with 1/24 horizontal resolution (approximately 4 km) and embedding the improvement described in the sections above. Model outputs are presented aggregating the state variables as follows:

- Total mercury (HgT) is the sum of all Hg species in the water (HgII, Hg0, MMHg, and DMHg)
- Methylmercury (MeHg) is the sum of organic Hg species in the water (MMHg, and DMHg)
- DGM is the sum of gaseous Hg species in the water (Hg0 and DMHg)

This aggregation is based on operational standards for laboratory analysis of field data. While in recent years new measurements of the individual Hg species are becoming available, most data are available as listed above (Table 7.5.2).

Cruise	tHg	DGM	MeHg	DMHg	MMHg	FHgT	FMMHg	PHgT	PMMHg	
EROS2000 1990	x									<i>Cossa et al., 1997</i>
EROS2000 1992	x									<i>Cossa et al., 1997</i>
URANIA 2000	x	x	x			x	x			<i>Horvat et al., 2003</i>
URANIA 2003	x	x	x			x	x			<i>Kotnik et al., 2007</i>
MERCYMS 2003-2004			x	x	x					<i>unpublished</i>
VEGA 2004	x		x							<i>Cossa et al., 2009</i>
URANIA 2004		x								<i>Vaupotič et al., 2015</i>
URANIA 2004 fall		x	x							<i>Kotnik et al., 2015</i>
URANIA 2005	x	x	x	x						<i>Kotnik et al., 2015</i>
MED-OCEANOR 2004	x		x							<i>Cossa et al., 2009</i>
BIOPRHOFI 2006	x	x	x							<i>Cossa et al., 2009</i>
DYCOMED 2007	x	x	x							<i>Heimbürger et al., 2010</i>
MED-OCEANOR 2009			x							<i>unpublished</i>
URANIA 2009		x								<i>Kotnik et al., 2017</i>
MED-OCEANOR 2010		x								<i>Fantozzi et al., 2013</i>
URANIA 2011	x	x	x							<i>Kotnik et al., 2017</i>
CASCADE 2011	x		x							<i>Cossa et al., 2017</i>
GOSHIP M84/3 2011			x							<i>Heimbürger et al., 2013</i>
FENICE 2012	x		x							<i>Cossa et al., 2022, Kotnik et al., 2017</i>
FENICE 2013			x							<i>unpublished</i>
GEOTRACES MEDBLACK 2013	x									<i>Rosati et al., 2018</i>
RV Bios Dva 2014										<i>Živković et al., 2019</i>
MINERVA 2015										<i>unpublished</i>
GEOTRACES PEACETIME 2017	x		x							<i>unpublished</i>
RV Antedon II f 2017-2019	x		x					x		<i>Jiskra et al., 2021</i>
FixO3 2018			x							<i>Rosati et al., in prep</i>
HIPPOCAMPE 2019	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	<i>unpublished</i>

Table 7.5.2. Metadata of the dataset on mercury field observation in the Mediterranean Sea compiled in the NECCTON project for model validation. tHg is total Hg, DGM is dissolved gaseous mercury, MeHg is methylmercury, DMHg is dimethylmercury, MMHg is monomethylmercury, FHgT and FMMHg are filtered species and PHgT and PMMHg are particulate species. Unpublished data are marked in orange. Published data are from Cossa et al., 1997, 2009, 2017; Fantozzi et al., 2013; Heimbürger et al., 2010, 2013; Horvat et al., 2003; Jiskra et al., 2021; Kotnik et al., 2007, 2015; Rosati et al., 2018; Vaupotič et al., 2008; Živković et al., 2019.

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The computational demand for the OGSTM-BFM-Hg model is larger than for the configuration including only the ecosystem model and not mercury dynamics (OGSTM-BFM model) due to the higher number of state variables (+12) and processes simulated and to the need of using a reduced timestep (300 seconds instead of 1800 at 1/16 resolution) to achieve model stability. Therefore, the initial plan was to start as a first step with a 1/16 resolution for the Neccton project, assuming the 1/24 was too much computational costly. However, the Italian provider of HPC facilities (CINECA) experienced severe damages to its infrastructures due to the flood that hit Casalecchio di Reno (BO) at the end of October 2024. This affected the project activity due to a complete down of the cluster G100 for running simulation for 1 month, and the inaccessibility of the storage system containing forcing files to run the model at 1/16 resolution, which is still ongoing up to date (26/2/2025). For this reason, a further effort was made to test and to implement the model code at 1/24 resolution, which required to recreate all the boundary (atmosphere, rivers, Gibraltar and Atlantic) and initial conditions for mercury for the new mesh. Although we approached the problem to turn it into an opportunity, these events clearly slowed down the workflow, limiting the possibility to investigate more in-depth model output. Further validation will be carried out before running the hindcast simulations using a dataset of field observations that cover the period 1990-2019 that has been compiled during the NECCTON project (Table 7.5.2 and Figure 7.5.4).

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Figure 7.5.4. Observational data of Hg species in the Mediterranean Sea (see Table 6.5.2) grouped by year after removing outlier. The colours indicate the depth of the sample.

A preliminary assessment of results shows that mercury species tend to increase in the most surficial water layer in the improved model version at 1/24 resolution compared to the baseline model version at 1/16 resolution (Figures 7.5.5-7.5.7), which also lead to an increase in the evasion of gaseous mercury (Figure 7.5.8). Total and methylmercury also increase at 120 m depth, while dissolved gaseous mercury slightly decrease at this depth compared to the baseline. This may be due to an increase in remineralization that favour the recycling of Hg species, to differences in the vertical diffusion as well as to other factors and will be further investigated in the future months.

Vertical profiles of monthly mean concentrations of MeHg in three sub-basins of the Mediterranean Sea (Southern Adriatic, Northwest Mediterranean, and Ionian Sea) for the two model runs are shown in Figure 7.5.9 compared with field data from Cossa et al., (2009) and Kotnik et al., (2017). This comparison was already performed in Rosati et al., (2022) for the simulated year 2017. Here, we analyse a different year (2015) due to the unavailability of model output for other years (see the technical issues stated above). First, we notice that the baseline model outputs for 2015 fit best to the observation than the baseline model outputs for 2017 shown in Rosati et al., (2022), pointing out at the importance of exploring interannual variability. In the upgraded version of the OGSTM-BFM-Hg model, the data-model agreement improves in the Northwest Mediterranean and Ionian Sea, while it diminishes in the Southern Adriatic. However, it should be noted that this comparison is based on a

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small set of non-synoptic observations from the early 2000s (2004-2006), and new unpublished data from the Southern Adriatic Sea collected in 2018 show very low concentration (0.1-0.2 pmol/l) of MeHg in most of the stations across a transect in the Southern Adriatic Pit (Cardin et al. 2019, Rosati et al., in prep.) consistent with the profiles simulated at 1/24. The Southern Adriatic is considered an “intermittently blooming” areas (D’Ortenzio e D’Alcalà, 2009) and thus is likely characterized by a higher interannual variability of methylmercury production than other Mediterranean subbasins.

Fig. 7.5.5. Average annual distribution of total Hg concentrations (pmol/l) in the water of the Mediterranean Sea at three depths simulated for 2015 with the OGSTM-BFM-Hg model. Left panels show output of the original model at 1/16 horizontal resolution (Rosati et al., 2022), and panels on the right-side show output of the improved model developed in the NECCTON project (see sections 7.2-7.4) run at 1/24 horizontal resolution.

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Fig. 7.5.6. As Figure 7.5.4 but for methylmercury (MeHg, which is the sum of MMHg and DMHg state variables). Concentrations are in pmol/l.

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Fig. 7.5.7. As Figure 7.5.4 but for dissolved gaseous mercury (DGM, which is the sum of Hg₀ and DMHg state variables). Concentrations are in pmol/l.

Fig. 7.5.8. Net exchange of gaseous elemental mercury (nmol m⁻² d⁻¹) over one year in the Mediterranean Sea simulated for 2015 with the OGSTM-BFM-Hg model. The left panel show output of the original model at 1/16 horizontal resolution (Rosati et al., 2022), and the panel on the right-side show output of the improved model developed in the NECCTON project (see sections 6.2-6.4) run at 1/24 horizontal resolution.

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Figure 7.5.9. Vertical profiles of monthly average MeHg (MMHg+DMHg) concentrations in the water column reproduced by OGSTM-BFM-Hg model for 2015. The left panel show output of the original model at 1/16 horizontal resolution (Rosati et al., 2022), and the panel on the right-side show output of the improved model developed in the NECCTON project (see sections 7.2-7.4) run at 1/24 horizontal resolution. The upper panels show the Southern Adriatic Sea, the intermediate panels the Northwestern Mediterranean, and the bottom panel the Ionian Sea.

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8. Oil

8.1 Introduction

The negative effects of oil spills on marine life, including plankton, fish, marine birds, turtles, and mammals, can be devastating and long-lasting. Spilled oil emits toxic volatile chemicals into the atmosphere, fouls shorelines, and destroys commercial fisheries, aquaculture, and shellfish beds. Oil-associated heavy metals can enter the food chain, accumulating in tissues and poisoning biota. Moreover, oil spillages can also seriously affect human health.

The petroleum hydrocarbon contamination is compounded by the recent inventory by Dong et al. (2022), who revealed that the present-day anthropogenic contribution to marine oil pollution may have been substantially underestimated. The Mediterranean's chronic oil pollution, recently reported by [SkyTruth Cerulean](#), also presents a negative picture.

Furthermore, the recent extreme oil spill in the Black Sea (over 3,000 tons of heavy fuel oil near the Kerch Strait, December 2024) revealed a deficiency in oil drift predictions and a general unpreparedness of the competent authorities.

In response to the current understanding of the harmful effects of pollution caused by petroleum hydrocarbons, the NECCON project has incorporated oil spill simulations into its integrated model-based approach, which combines pelagic, benthic, and nekton biogeochemical cycles with pollutants as environmental stressors.

The project transcends disciplinary boundaries by exploring new data streams. This is in line with a [Digital Twin Ocean](#) concept, which necessitates the digitalization of our knowledge of the ocean.

The NECCON-2023 stakeholder survey summarized in [Deliverable D8.1](#) showed that ~34% of respondents from 84 representatives from 45 countries declared their interest in oil pollution-related products.

8.2 Oil transport and weathering

8.2.1 Background

The [MEDSLIK-II](#) Lagrangian oil spill model (De Dominicis et al., 2013) is a free-access community model that has been successfully used for over 12 years to simulate the transport and fate of oil spills. A full list of the published MEDSLIK-II applications can be found on the corresponding website.

In the model framework, the oil slick is divided into constituent particles. The problem is represented by stochastic differential equations, which consider the advection of particles by currents, wind (the so-called wind drift), and waves. External oceanographic and atmospheric models or observations provide data on these drivers. Turbulent diffusion is represented as a three-dimensional random walk process. Three states of a particle are considered: floating on the sea surface, dispersed in the water column, and attached to the coastline or beached. For a given particle, the state transition is governed by oil transformations in the environment.

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These transformations are computed through bulk formulae, which formalize the changes in thick and thin oil volumes due to three main processes known collectively as weathering: viscous-gravity spreading, evaporation, and natural dispersion. The formation of water-in-oil emulsion is also considered. The model simulates the adsorption of particles into the coastal environment, taking into account the likelihood of being washed back into the water.

With MEDSLIK-II, we compute the geographical coordinates of particles at each time step. By binning the particles of each state, we obtain oil concentrations at the sea surface C_S , dispersed in the water column C_D , along coastlines C_C , and sedimented at the bottom C_B (Fig. 8.2.1).

Fig. 8.2.1 Schematic representation of the oil concentration classes (the grey circles represent the oil particles and L_C – the coastline).

The code for this model can be found on GitHub at https://github.com/Sliubartseva/MEDSLIK_II_NECCTON.

8.2.2. Theory

The model represents the oil concentration at the surface C_S and the oil concentration dispersed in the water column C_D . Therefore, the oil weathering equation is comprehended as follows:

$$\frac{dC_S}{dt} = \frac{\rho dV_S}{A dt},$$

$$\frac{dC_D}{dt} = \frac{\rho dV_D}{A dt},$$

where A is the unit area, V_S is the surface oil slick volume, V_D is the dispersed oil volume, and ρ is the seawater density.

Regarding the surface oil which arrives close to the coasts and is adsorbed, the concentration of beached oil is given by

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$$C_c(x, t) = \frac{\rho}{L_c} V_c,$$

where L_c is a coastline segment length and V_c is an adsorbed oil volume calculated from the oil particle state variables.

The weathering works in the upper sea layer and comprehends three main processes: evaporation, which occurs first and mainly acts on the lighter fractions of the oil, dispersion of the remaining oil fractions below the water surface; and spreading, which is responsible for the mechanical spreading of the spill over the water surface under the action of gravitational force (Fig. 8.2.2).

Fig. 8.2.2 Weathering processes using Mackay's approach. **TK** indicates the thick slick and **TN** -the thin slick. V^{TK} and V^{TN} are the surface oil volumes of the thick and thin part of the slick and the suffixes indicate evaporation (E), dispersion (D), and spreading (S).

Consequently, the weathering processes are considered separately for the thick slick and thin slick and the prognostic equations are:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dV^{TK}}{dt} &= - \frac{dV^{TK}}{dt} \Big|_{(E)} - \frac{dV^{TK}}{dt} \Big|_{(D)} - \frac{dV^{TN}}{dt} \Big|_{(S)} \\ \frac{dV^{TN}}{dt} &= - \frac{dV^{TN}}{dt} \Big|_{(E)} - \frac{dV^{TN}}{dt} \Big|_{(D)} + \frac{dV^{TN}}{dt} \Big|_{(S)} \end{aligned}$$

where the suffixes indicate evaporation (E), dispersion (D), and spreading (S).

All the oil slick state variables are defined only at the slick's central geographical position (Gravity Centre, hereinafter GC), which is updated after each time step. Parameterization of the weathering processes is detailed in De Dominicis et al. (2013). Initially, the model solves the weathering equations and then solves the advection-diffusion equations.

To solve the latter with a Lagrangian particle formalism, the oil slick is initially discretized in N_{TOT} particles with associated particle state variables and then the oil concentration is computed by assembling the particles with their associated properties.

The horizontal current field used in the Lagrangian model is taken to be the sum of different components:

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$$\begin{cases} \sigma = 0, & d\mathbf{x}_k(t) = [\mathbf{U}_C(x_k, y_k, 0, t) + \mathbf{U}_W(x_k, y_k, 0, t) + \\ & + \mathbf{U}_S(x_k, y_k, 0, t) + \mathbf{U}_D(x_k, y_k, 0, t)]dt + d\mathbf{x}'_k(t), \\ \sigma = 1, & d\mathbf{x}_k(t) = \mathbf{U}_C(x_k, y_k, z_k, t)dt + d\mathbf{x}'_k(t), \end{cases}$$

where σ is the particle status index which identifies if a particle is on the sea surface ($\sigma=0$) or dispersed into the water column ($\sigma=1$), U_C is the ocean current velocity field, U_W is the local wind velocity correction term (wind drift term), U_S , called hereafter wave current term, is the velocity due to wave-induced currents or the surface Stokes drift, U_D is the wind drag correction due to emergent part of the objects at the surface and $dx'_k(t)$ is the displacement due to the turbulent diffusion.

In the model, the turbulent diffusion is parameterized with a random walk scheme as follows:

$$d\mathbf{x}'_k(t) = \sqrt{6Kdt}\mathbf{Z},$$

where \mathbf{K} is the turbulent diffusion diagonal tensor and \mathbf{Z} is a vector of independent random numbers distributed uniformly. The three components of \mathbf{K} are K_h, K_h, K_v .

To calculate the Stokes drift, MEDSLIK-II uses the empirical, so-called JONSWAP wave spectrum as a function of wind speed and fetch (Hasselmann et al., 1973).

8.2.3 Implementation

To solve coherently the weathering and the advection-diffusion equations, an algorithm, which links the oil slick, and the particle state variables is needed. The model sequential solution method is represented schematically in Fig. 8.2.3.

A surface oil release into the marine environment can be instantaneous or continuous: in the first case, all the oil is spilled instantly, while in the latter the leakage may last for several hours or even months. Furthermore, the simulated scenario could involve a polygonal oil slick detected from a satellite or UAV (Uninhabited Aerial Vehicle).

The continuous oil spill release is modelled by dividing the total spilled oil into several sub-spills consisting of a given part of the oil released at the spill location during the prescribed computational time interval. As each sub-spill is moved away from the source, the total spill becomes a chain of sub-spills. In the continuous release, a given fraction of the total amount of particles used in the simulation is released with each sub-spill.

In the case of an instantaneous release, at the beginning of the simulation, all the oil is released on the sea surface at the spill location, and all the particles are released instantaneously.

Satellite, overflight, or UAV (Uninhabited Aerial Vehicle) detected slicks are modelled as instantaneous spills except for the fact that the total amount of oil and particles of each slick are released inside the polygon which identifies the shape of the slicks. The data required to define the initial oil spill condition are:

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- location: i.e., the geographical coordinates of the oil source location. In the case of a detected slick, the polygon contour/s has to be specified;
- start time: i.e., the start time of the spill or the time of the slick detection;
- volume: i.e., the total amount of oil released in a spill or the total oil amount of the detected slick;
- duration: i.e., spill duration (for instantaneous or detected slicks, it is zero);
- age: i.e., the period from initial arrival in the sea. This information can be provided by satellite-, overflight- or UAV-based monitoring systems.

Fig. 8.2.3 MEDSLIK-II workflow.

The forward Euler method is utilized for the numerical solution of the transport equation. At each time step, the Lagrangian velocity field at the particle position is computed performing a linear interpolation in time between successive input velocity fields and bi-linear interpolation over the horizontal space using the four external field grid points of the Eulerian model field (oceanographic or meteorological) nearest the particle position. Over the vertical, a linear interpolation between two Eulerian model levels is applied. The [MEDSLIK-II NECCTON](#) code was run with the default timestep of 30 min.

8.3 Validation

The test case below illustrates the simulation of an oil spill scenario related to the historical HAVEN oil spill that took place off the Port of Genoa in April 1991.

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This oil spill accident was recognized not only as the largest shipwreck in European waters but also as one of the worst oil pollution cases in the Mediterranean. We specified the simplified HAVEN oil spill scenario as follows:

- starting time of the spill was 15th April 1991 at 15:30 pm;
- initial polygons were provided by METEO FRANCE;
- the continuous 50-hour release with a spill rate of 200 ton/hour gave the total spilled oil volume of 10,000 tons;
- the type of the oil was heavy Iranian crude oil (API = 31);
- the simulation length was chosen until 29th April, when the last spill observations were documented;
- the Stokes drift was taken into account using the empirical JONSWAP parameterization.

Figure 8.2.4 shows a test case snapshot to demonstrate the performance of the MEDSLIK-II code.

Fig. 8.2.4 A Snapshot of the test case. Sea surface oil concentration is represented in colour scale. The wind vector corresponds to the gravity centre of the slick. Beached oil concentrations $< 1 \text{ ton km}^{-1}$ are depicted in brown, $\geq 1 \text{ ton km}^{-1}$ – in black.

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9. Fisheries pressure

9.1 Introduction

In the marine environment, bottom trawl fisheries represent a dominant driver of sea floor ecosystem change, especially due to its deleterious effect on benthic life (Jennings & Kaiser 1998; Thrush & Dayton 2002). In spite of the negative effects of this practice on ecosystem services, considerable social and economic issues are at stake when envisaging a reduction of fishing effort. Hence, fisheries stakeholders and managers are constrained in their decision leeway and must find optimal trade-offs between human and environmental costs.

NIOZ built a new R package (“Bfiat”) endowed with functionalities that enable researchers as well as managers to assess the vulnerability of benthic organisms and associated ecosystem functions to bottom trawling (Beauchard and Soetaert, 2026). Based on the literature that includes theoretical and applied aspects, we implemented the related knowledge into a deterministic modelling framework.

The Bfiat package enables the prediction of benthic state following different trawling disturbance scenarios as a fraction of pre-disturbance biotic state. Benthic state is predicted according to species-specific logistic population growth descriptions combined with trawling parameters and organism response traits. While trawling parameters determine the type of disturbance, taxon-specific functional traits act as drivers of biotic resistance or vulnerability in the model response.

The model will be applied on the Black Sea northwestern shelf. Moreover, given the long-term NIOZ expertise on the North Sea Benthos, the same application was conducted over the North Sea shelf. The code for the model can be found on GitHub at <https://github.com/EMODnet/Bfiat>.

9.2 Fisheries disturbance

9.2.1 Background

A surge of ecological indicator developments has taken place the last fifteen years to support marine ecosystem management (Beauchard et al. 2017; Miatta 2021), especially in European waters under the impulse of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (European Community 2008). However, rare are the indicators that directly relate state to pressure as part of the pressure-response-state framework (OECD 1993; Bowen & Riley 2003). What has been missing is a deterministic approach that returns benthic state as a direct function of pressure or that allows to forecast future benthic state under current or modulated trawling pressure.

To fill this gap, the R package “Bfiat” enables such kind of predictions with flexible applications. The provided model calculates species response to bottom trawling disturbance using the logistic growth formulation. Its parameters are derived from organism abundance data from a particular site combined with species trait information, especially age at maturity and the depth of occurrence in the

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sediment. The outcome of the model describes the trajectories of species abundances over time. Such changes modulate ecosystem functions that are ensured by the species community. For instance, sediment bio-mixing and bio-irrigation (i.e., bioturbation; Kristensen et al. 2012) are ecosystem functions that affect sediment biogeochemistry and that can be quantified by specific species traits in combination with abundances. Hence, beyond simple abundance, the Bfiat package also provides opportunities to assess sea floor functional vulnerability.

9.2.2. Theory

Fisheries disturbance on the benthos can be modelled based on the logistic growth equation that describes how benthic organism density evolves following disturbance (i.e., between trawling events). The model reads:

$$\frac{dD_i^t}{dt} = r_i \cdot D_i^t \cdot \left(1 - \frac{D_i^t}{K_i}\right) \quad (1)$$

D_i^t is the density of species i at a particular time t , K_i is the carrying capacity of species i and r_i is the logistic growth parameter (units [1/time]). The parameters r_i and K_i are specific for species i ; the carrying capacity K_i also depends on the site where the species is found (e.g., local resource availability, predation or competition).

The effect of trawling on benthic population growth can be included in a model in two ways:

- Local applications consider trawling to occur as a series of successive events (e.g., yearly) that instantaneously deplete benthic populations. Between these events, the populations can recover to a certain proportion of their initial states (Fig. 9.2.1).
- Regional applications consider the effect of trawling on a larger area, where fishing can be considered to occur continuously, albeit each time at different locations. Here, the average benthic population size at the larger scale is modelled whereby trawling is imposed as a cause of constant mortality.

In models that describe a population at a small scale, trawling is considered a disturbance that has a relatively high impact on benthic population size. When species community is trawled, at times t_j , the density of each species i is instantaneously reduced:

$$D_i^{t_j^+} = D_i^{t_j^-} \cdot (1 - d_i) \quad (2)$$

where $D_i^{t_j^+}$ and $D_i^{t_j^-}$ are the densities immediately after and before trawling at time t_j , respectively; d_i is the depletion fraction. Between trawling events, and starting from the initial condition $D_i^{t_j^-}$, the population recovers according to equation (1). The average time between trawling events (in years) can be estimated from the annual swept area ratio S , as $1/S$. Thus, if trawling occurs on regular intervals, the time at which fishing occurs is given by:

$$t_j = t_{j-1} + 1/S \quad (3)$$

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Figure 9.2.1. Illustration of logistic model-based trawling effect on a local benthic organism population. Y-axis, percentage of initial faunal density D (e.g., individual organism or biomass density); 100 % as carrying capacity K , D/K expressing the benthic state. Continuous blue line, faunal density according to the local model with disturbance frequency is fixed to 1 trawling event per year. The effect of the trawling gear entails an instantaneous mortality in exposed organisms (1). Over the longer-term, the recovery (at an intrinsic rate of natural increase r) operates until the next disturbance (2); see equation (1) for r and K coefficients. Dashed blue line, continuous model according to equation (5). If the recovery does not compensate for the depletion, the density decreases to a level at which the organisms represent the resilient fraction of the population (steady-state D^* from equation (6)).

Over a large area, trawling pressure can be considered homogeneous in time and space. Here the trawling pressure is added to the differential equation that reads (Pitcher et al., 2017):

$$\frac{dD_i^t}{dt} = r_i \cdot D_i^t \cdot \left(1 - \frac{D_i^t}{K_i}\right) - m_i \cdot D_i^t \quad (4)$$

where m_i is the mortality, on average induced by trawling in the area on species i (unit [1/time]).

9.2.3 Implementation

The fishing impact models run in the open-source framework R (R core team 2024) and have been implemented in the Bfiat R-package (Soetaert et al. 2022). Biological density and biomass data and trait composition data, used for the fisheries impact analysis on ecosystem functioning, are compiled in the R-package Btrait (Soetaert and Beauchard 2022) that also contains functions to work on density and trait datasets.

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The two phases of faunal response to trawling disturbance as shown in Figure 9.2.1 involve specific traits. Within a species community, the instantaneous depletion d_i of species i depends on organism sensitivity to physical damage. A trait that obviously determines organism exposure to trawling gear is sediment burying depth. To parameterise d_i , we assume that depletion depends on the overlap between gear penetration depth (p_G) and burying depth, which is parameterised as:

$$d_i = \sum_{z=[z_u, z_l]} m_d \cdot \max(0, p_G - z_u) \cdot f_{i[z_u, z_l]} \quad (5)$$

with z_u and z_l respectively the upper and lower boundaries of the sediment layer, and f_i the fraction of the total community density in that layer. m_d is a linear coefficient that scales the depletion to the depth impacted by the gear (unit cm^{-1}). The $\max(0, p_G - z_u)$ part ensures that $d_i = 0$ when the gear does not penetrate the layer. As d_i shows an asymptotic relationship with p_G in Hiddink et al. (2017), the depletion fraction of any species is limited to 0.42, the maximum in Hiddink et al. (2017):

$$d_i = \min(d_i, 0.42) \quad (6)$$

Based on this simple formulation, only the value of the mortality parameter m_d needs to be estimated. We estimate the parameter by fitting this function to data in Hiddink et al. (2017), who, based on a meta-analysis, quantified community depletion fraction as a function of gear penetration depth. A value for the mortality coefficient $m_d = 0.055 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ gives a good fit to the data (see below).

The second phase of faunal response to trawling disturbance is a progressive faunal recovery towards the species carrying capacity, in absence of new trawling disturbance. This phase is best expressed by the intrinsic rate of natural increase r as the per capita instantaneous rate of population increase for stable age distribution (Stearns, 1992), but it is missing for most of species. r is proportional to inversed age at sexual maturity (Savage et al., 2004). We compiled r values for 56 marine macrozoobenthic species to determine r_i as a direct function of age maturity α_i :

$$r_i = \frac{2.26}{\alpha_i} \quad (7)$$

The carrying capacity K_i is estimated assuming that the measured species density D^* is at equilibrium with the prevailing trawling intensity S . Then the carrying capacity can be estimated as:

$$K_i = \frac{D_i^*}{1 + \frac{S}{r_i} \ln(1 - d_i)} \quad (8)$$

9.3 Validation

There exist few data that document the impact of fisheries on benthic systems. Most of such data were compiled in Hiddink et al. (2017, 2019). We used these data for model calibration. For instance, we used the total benthic biomass depletion for otter trawls, beam trawls, towed dredge and hydraulic

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dredge as in Hiddink et al. (2017) to derive a taxon-specific depletion rate, based on the overlap of the vertical position of taxa in the sediment with the penetration depth of the fishing gear.

As a validation of the model and its parameterisations, we then argued that the model should not predict a species to become extinct at a fished site when the species is abundantly observed at that site.

The model was applied on the Dutch sector of the North Sea where abundant data are present (Beauchard et al. 2022). The data are available in the Btrait R package (Soetaert & Beauchard, 2022) and comprise the densities of more than 400 taxa, in 102 stations (102 with non-null organism abundance since 2009). We considered the concomitant availability of faunal and trawling data, from 2009 to 2018. For each species in all stations, we back-calculated the carrying capacity K (equation (8)) to define an untrawled state and estimated the depletion fraction using equation (6), for disturbances with a growing gear penetration into the sediment. From the species-depletion rates, the community depletion for each station was estimated and compared to the data. The results, using a depletion parameter $m_d = 0.055 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, accurately followed the experimental measurements compiled in Hiddink et al. (2017). For each station, we ran the procedure through 1000 resampling with replacement of the faunal occurrences to derive a 95 % confidence interval (Fig. 9.2.2).

Figure 9.2.2. Community depletion as a fraction of the total community individual density. Each blue line represents the summed response of the species in each of the 102 stations, to increased penetration depth into the sediment; grey dashed lines, lower 2.5 and upper 97.5 % limits of confidence intervals; the 4 black dots represent data from Hiddink et al. 2017, provided in Pitcher et al. (2022), with mean \pm 95 % propagated CI; from left to right: otter trawl, beam trawl, towed dredge and hydraulic dredge, respectively.

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10. Conclusion

This deliverable presents the key advancements in Tasks 8.2 and 8.3, focusing on the development and refinement of numerical models to simulate the fate, transport, and occurrence of major pressures to the marine environments, to their ecosystems and ecosystems services: microplastics, persistent organic pollutants (POPs), mercury, oil spills, fisheries-related and climate-induced stressors.

Several modelling frameworks have been improved, harmonised and applied to the different European regional seas to build the new modelling capability for CMEMS to respond to emerging needs in marine environmental monitoring and policy support.

Key processes such as fragmentation, biofouling, and particle ageing of microplastics has been substantially improved. These developments enable more accurate simulations of particle size distributions and sinking behaviour, improving our understanding of microplastic transport and potential ingestion by marine organisms. A new module of persistent organic pollutants, (POPs), was implemented to simulate photodegradation, bioaccumulation, and sorption dynamics. Mercury modelling has benefited from new development of the DOC cycling in the biogeochemical model. This allows for more realistic predictions of mercury bioaccumulation and cycling within marine food webs. For oil spills, the model now includes refined processes related to oil transport and weathering, significantly improving the ability to forecast dispersion patterns and degradation rates under varying environmental conditions. New indicators of fisheries pressure have been developed to assess the spatial extent and intensity of bottom trawling disturbances on benthic habitats. These allow for a more detailed characterization of ecosystem impacts and contribute to strategies for sustainable fisheries management. Finally, climate-related stressors, such as changes in temperature, dissolved oxygen, and pH, have been assessed using biogeochemical model outputs. This enables the quantification of long-term environmental trends and spatial patterns of change, supporting cumulative impact assessments and the identification of ecosystem vulnerabilities.

Initial validation efforts have been carried out through comparison with observational datasets, with more comprehensive intercomparison and benchmarking planned in collaboration with CMEMS and other WPs.

These developments collectively support NECCTON's broader ambition to improve marine monitoring and prediction capabilities. The work presented in D8.2 lays the groundwork for the development of next-generation Copernicus products that can track pollutant dynamics, assess ecosystem health, and inform policy decisions. These updates strengthen our capacity for assessing environmental risks and informing policy frameworks aligned with the Stockholm Convention, the EU Zero pollution action plan, the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), contributing also to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Looking ahead, future efforts should primarily aim to:

- Integrate high trophic level dynamics into pollution models to account for bioaccumulation and food-web level interactions.

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- Advance model coupling to assess cumulative pressures.
- Increase model resolution.
- Increase the number of pollutants and pressures, selected based on their toxicity and persistence in the marine environment and considering also human health.

This will be addressed in the continuation of the project, in particular in the synthesis report of product quality (Deliverable 9.1), in the case-study report on the product exploitation (Deliverable 9.2) and in the roadmap for transfer of NECCTON products to the Copernicus Marine Service (Deliverable 2.3).

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